

**“DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF *FUSOBACTERIUM
NECROPHORUM LktA* GENE FROM FOOTROT OF SHEEP AND
GOATS IN ANDHRA PRADESH”**

By

Y.SREEHARSHA

B.V.Sc & A.H

TVM/2016-019

Thesis Submitted To

SRI VENKATESWARA VETERINARY UNIVERSITY

In partial fulfilment of the requirements

For the award of the degree of

MASTER OF VETERINARY SCIENCE

In The Faculty of Veterinary Science

(VETERINARY MICROBIOLOGY)

DEPARTMENT OF VETERINARY MICROBIOLOGY

COLLEGE OF VETERINARY SCIENCE

TIRUPATI – 517 502 (A.P) INDIA.

FEBRUARY 2019

CERTIFICATE

Y.SREEHARSHA, I.D.NO: TVM/2016-019 has satisfactorily prosecuted the course of research and that the thesis entitled **“DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF *FUSOBACTERIUM NECROPHORUM* *LktA* GENE FROM FOOTROT OF SHEEP AND GOATS IN ANDHRA PRADESH”** submitted is the result of original research work and is of sufficiently high standard to warrant its presentation to the examination. I also certify that the thesis or part thereof has not been previously submitted by him for a degree of any university.

Date:

Place:

Major Advisor
(Dr. N. VINOD KUMAR)
Associate Professor
Department of Veterinary Microbiology
College of Veterinary Science
Tirupati-517501.

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF *FUSOBACTERIUM NECROPHORUM LktA* GENE FROM FOOTROT OF SHEEP AND GOATS IN ANDHRA PRADESH**” submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of **MASTER OF VETERINARY SCIENCE** of the Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University is a record of the bonafide research work carried out by **Y.SREEHARSHA** under my guidance and supervision. The student’s Advisory committee has approved the subject of the thesis.

No part of the thesis has been submitted for any other degree or diploma. The author of the thesis has duly acknowledged all the assistance and help received during the course of investigation.

(Dr. N. VINOD KUMAR)
Chairman of the Advisory Committee

Thesis approved by the Student’s Advisory Committee

Chairman: Dr. N. VINOD KUMAR _____
Associate Professor
Department of Veterinary Microbiology
College of Veterinary Science
Tirupati-517502.

Member: Dr. R.K. CHAITANYA _____
Assistant Professor
Department of Veterinary Microbiology
College of Veterinary Science
Tirupati- 517 502.

Member: Dr. K. SUJATHA _____
Professor
Department of Veterinary Pathology
College of Veterinary Science
Tirupati – 517 502.

DECLARATION

I, **Y.SREEHARSHA (ID NO: TVM/2016-019)** hereby declare that the thesis entitled “**DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF *FUSOBACTERIUM NECROPHORUM LktA* GENE FROM FOOTROT OF SHEEP AND GOATS IN ANDHRA PRADESH**” submitted to Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupati for the degree of “**MASTER OF VETERINARY SCIENCE**” is the result of original research done by me. I also declare that the material contained in this thesis has not been published earlier.

Date:
Place: Tirupati

(Y.SREEHARSHA)

CONTENTS

CHAPTER NO	TITLE	PAGE NO
I	INTRODUCTION	1-3
II	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	4-30
III	MATERIALS AND METHODS	31-40
IV	RESULTS	41-63
V	DISCUSSION	64-73
VI	SUMMARY	74-76
	LITERATURE CITED	77-102
	APPENDIX	103

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE NO.	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1.	Details of Samples collection	31
2.	Details of lktA primers designed in the lab	33
3.	Details of Primers dilutions for Duplex PCR	36
4.	<i>F. necrophorum</i> DNA dilutions	44
5.	<i>D. nodosus</i> DNA dilutions	44
6.	Samples positive for footrot	51
7.	Details of statistical analysis	54
8.	Nucleotide and corresponding amino acid substitutions of <i>lktA</i> Gene aligned sequences	58

LIST OF FIGURES

FIG NO.	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1.	Collection of Foot swabs	41
2.	Collection of Gingival Swabs	41
3.	Necrosis of inner hoof	42
4.	Interdigital dermatitis	42
5.	Interdigital dermatitis	42
6.	Severe hoof erosion	42
7.	Interdigital dermatitis Score 1	43
8.	Interdigital dermatitis Score 2	43
9.	Interdigital dermatitis Score 3	43
10.	Interdigital dermatitis Score 4	43
11.	Duplex PCR sensitivity in detecting different conc of DNA	45
12.	Agarose gel showing the PCR amplification of 16S rRNA gene	46
13.	Agarose gel showing the PCR amplification of LktA gene	47
14.	Duplex PCR with different conc. of primers	48
15.	Duplex PCR with different concentrations of DNA	49
16.	Duplex PCR with field sample	50
17.	Comparison of <i>D. nodosus</i> positives in sheep and goat	52
18.	Comparison of of <i>F. necrophorum</i> positives in sheep and goat	52
19.	Percent of combined presence of <i>D.nodosus</i> and <i>F.necrophorum</i> in sheep and goats	53
20.	Details of total Fn = <i>F. necrophorum</i> , and Dn = <i>D. nodosus</i>	53
21.	Multiple sequence alignment of partial lktA gene sequences of <i>F.necrophorum</i> .	55
22.	Sequence alignment of partial lktA gene sequences of <i>F.necrophorum</i>	56
23.	Amino acid sequences of the multiple alignment with substitutions at various locations.	57
24.	Evolutionary relationships of 12 taxa	59
25.	LktA full genome (AF312861) circular presentation with partial sequences	62

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First and foremost, I offer my praises and thanks to the almighty lord of seven hills for giving me strength to complete the research work.

*I wish to express my deep sense of gratitude and indebtedness to the chairman of my advisory committee, **Dr. N. Vinod Kumar**, Associate Professor, Department of Veterinary Microbiology, College of Veterinary Science, Triupati for his constant encouragement excellent guidance and providing necessary facilities throughout this investigation and for his continuous help, valuable guidance and endless encouragement during the course of investigation. The determining interest, critically going through the manuscript and also spending time in correction, execution, compilation and preparation of the thesis are invaluable in preparation of the manuscript. Under his guidance I successfully overcame many difficulties and learnt a lot. His own zeal for perfection, passion, unflinching courage and conviction has always inspired me to do more. He has inspired me and helped me realize the power of critical reasoning with constructive criticism in preparation of thesis.*

*I am very much thankful to **Dr. B. Sreedevi**, Professor and Head of Veterinary Microbiology, College of Veterinary Science, Tirupati for her support and encouragement for completion of thesis*

*I express my sincere thanks to **Dr. K. Sujatha**, Professor, Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary Science, Tirupati and member of the advisory committee for her valuable suggestions, critical comments during the period of research work and in preparation of thesis*

*I am especially morally bound to express my sincere thanks to, **Dr. R.K. Chaitanya** Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Tirupati and member of the advisory committee for extending all the help necessary for my course work and research work.*

*I wish to express my sincere thanks to **Dr.S. Vijayalakshmi**, Assistant Professor, College of Veterinary Sciences, Tirupati for her timely help, unstinted cooperation, constant encouragement and affection rendered during the period of my study.*

*I am pleased to thank **Dr. T. Nagendra Reddy**, Assistant Professor Department of Veterinary Microbiology for his initiative attempts, constant encouragement and help extended during the process of research.*

*I thank veterinary doctors **Dr. Suman, Dr. Prasad, Dr. Someshwar, Dr. Ram Chandra Reddy** for helping in sample collection*

*The lack of vocabulary fails me to express my indebtedness to **A. Karthik**, for his invaluable help in collecting clinical samples.*

*It is the correct time to express my heartfelt thanks to my affectionate friends and classmates **Madhava, Priyanka, Pushpalatha, Mounika, Girisha** who have been a great source of encouragement and help during the pursuit of my studies.*

*I thank, **Mr. Subramanyam Reddy, Mr. Bharadwaj, Mr. Gopal**, for their co-operation and affectionate help during my studies.*

*I thank **Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University** for providing monetary support in the form of stipend to prosecute my post graduation study.*

*A word of appreciation goes to **Sri Sai Graphics** for his timely and neat execution of thesis.*

*Finally it is because of the profuse love of my Parents **Sri. Y. Yerrama Reddy** and **Y. Padmalatha**, brother **Sreenidhi** who have been my source of strength and inspiration. They have stood by me all along.*

Name of the Author : **Y.SREEHARSHA**
Title of the thesis : **DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
FUSOBACTERIUM NECROPHORUM lktA
GENE FROM FOOTROT OF SHEEP AND
GOATS IN ANDHRA PRADESH.**
Degree to which it is Submitted : **Master of Veterinary Science**
Faculty : **Faculty of Veterinary Science**
Department : **Department of Veterinary Microbiology, College
of Veterinary Science, Tirupati - 517502.**
Guide : **Dr. N. VINOD KUMAR**
University : **Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupati**
Year of submission : **2019.**

ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to investigate *F. necrophorum* as a causative agent in footrot of sheep and goats in Andhra Pradesh and find causal association of *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* using duplex PCR.

A total of 172 samples were collected from Chittoor, Nellore, Kadapa, Ananthapur, and East Godavari Districts and screened for *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* using the duplex PCR standardised in the laboratory as a sensitive and simple molecular tool. Among 172 samples tested, 43(25%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, 18 (10.46%) for *F. necrophorum* and 34 (19.8%) for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*, in sheep 3 (2.9%) were *F. necrophorum*, 30 (29.1%) were of *D. nodosus*. Where as in goats 15 (21.7%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* no positives for *D. nodosus* and 18 (26%) with both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*, with significant association between the *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus*.

The lktA gene characterisation was done by comparing the local published sequences (KP226806; KP226805) with Genbank sequences selected revealed 99% homology with sequences from Australia, New Zealand and China. The sequences from

Australia, India (Jammu), and China showed variation at different positions ranging from 34 to 311 with these gaps at 69-71 with few exceptions at positions T79C, G81A, T165C, T166A, T245G, A251G, C288T and did not show any changes in the amino acid sequence. The phylogenetic analysis showed that lktA sequence (KP226805) showed distant clade and (KP226806) had shown to be root for other taxas of (KP226805; JX648295; JX678873; KY130428; FJ230831) from New Zealand, China, Australia and India_AP in the cluster. The other cluster sequences from India_UP (KJ404071) and India_kashmir (JF911484) showed 100% homology in the distinct clade.

This investigation was done as a preliminary initiative to demonstrate the association of *F. necrophorum* with *D. nodosus* in causing footrot in sheep and goat by simple molecular tool. Further epidemiological studies are required to arrive at a conclusion in finding the extent of involvement of *F. necrophorum* in footrot and strain variation of *F. necrophorum* in sheep and goat footrot cases in the region.

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

°C	-	Degree centigrade
µm	-	Micro metre
µl	-	Micro litre
/	-	Per
+ve	-	Positive
%	-	Percentage
&	-	and
@	-	At the rate of
i. e.	-	That is
hr	-	Hour
pH	-	Negative logarithm of hydrogen ion concentration
16S rRNA	-	RNA sequence of small subunit of bacterial ribosome
BD	-	Becton and Dickinson
bp	-	Base pairs
lktA	-	Leukotoxin gene
DAHDF	-	Department of Animal husbandry, Dairying and Fisheries
Dn	-	<i>Dichelobacter nodosus</i>
DNA	-	Deoxyribo Nucleic Acid
dNTP	-	Deoxynucleotide triphosphates
ELISA	-	Enzyme Linked Immuno Sorbent Assay
Fig	-	Figure
Fn	-	<i>Fusobacterium necrophorum</i>
kbp	-	Kilo base pairs
kDa	-	Kilo daltons
M	-	Molar
MgCl ₂	-	Magnesium Chloride
min	-	Minutes
mM	-	Milli Molar
mm	-	Milli metre
No. / n	-	Number
PBS	-	Phosphate Buffered Saline

PCR	-	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PFGE	-	Pulsed Field Gel Electrophoresis
pg	-	Pico gram
p mol/ μ l	-	Pico mole per micro litre
RBC	-	Red Blood Cells
rpm	-	Revolutions per minute
S. No	-	Serial number
UK	-	United Kingdom
USA	-	United States of America
UV	-	Ultra violet

CHAPTER-I

INTRODUCTION

Sheep and Goat rearing plays a crucial part in the agrarian economy of low-income sections of the society in rural areas in India. Income generated through sheep and goat rearing is mainly from meat and wool, due to its importance sheep and goat welfare has attracted a major attention in production. According to 19th Livestock census, India, sheep population is 63.78 millions and goat population constitutes 12.9 millions in rural areas where the importance of sheep and goat production is considered at a higher level.

Farmers with low income choose sheep and goat rearing as it involves less capital investment, early gains, and low feeding cost. The small ruminants are highly proliferative in terms of production compared to large ruminants. Sheep and goat are seasonal in production and yield good blooming of numbers in the flocks for starting a new production cycle. Hence, sheep and goat rearing is most widely practiced for livelihood of farmers.

Successful sheep and goat rearing involves management of various factors, from availability of proper nutrition, shelter to comfort from unusual weather conditions and predators, protection to many viral, bacterial and parasitic diseases like, Peste des petitis ruminants (PPR), Foot and mouth disease (FMD), sheep and goat pox, Contagious caprine pleuropneumonia (CCPP), Fascioliasis, distomatosis, enterotoxaemia, anthrax which result in mortality and morbidity losses, resulting in low productivity.

Among these, Footrot is an emerging infectious and contagious disease of sheep and goats causing severe lameness leading to productivity loss. It is caused specifically by the synergistic action of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, initially leading to interdigital dermatitis followed by the development of lesions on the interdigital wall of the hoof. The disease constitutes a major animal welfare problem apart from productivity losses due to the painful nature of the lesions.

Footrot is prevalent in countries that have temperate climate with moderate to heavy rainfall, such as Australia, New Zealand, United Kingdom, Sweden and Norway. The prevalence of the disease was initially reported in temperate of north Indian states, Jammu and Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh paradoxically. Footrot has also been reported from the south Indian states of Andhra Pradesh (A.P) and Kerala where the tropical climate prevails and temperature may rise to 47°C in summer season.

The disease is considered to be chronic and endemic in A.P and causes substantial economic loss through loss of body weight, decreased lambing percentage, distress sale of the affected sheep and the expenditure associated with prevention and treatment programmes.

Dichelobacter nodosus is an causative agent of footrot in ruminants, particularly in sheep, goats and cattle. The diagnosis of footrot is tedious and time consuming and complicated by the fastidious growth requirements and slow growing nature of *D. nodosus*.

Among the other causative agents, *F. necrophorum*, present in the environment, a Gram-negative anaerobe associated with human and animal diseases,

plays a substantial role in causing footrot. Initially, *F. necrophorum* was thought to be a secondary invader but it has been proved to cause disease independently.

Fusobacterium necrophorum has various virulence factors, that include endotoxin, leukotoxin, haemagglutinin, capsule, adhesins, platelet aggregation factor and certain extracellular enzymes. Among these, leukotoxin encoded by *lktA* gene is highly unique in this organism and plays a substantial role in pathology of footrot. Hence this work was undertaken to study the causal association of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in footrot in sheep and goats, and characterize the *lktA* gene partial sequences of *F. necrophorum*.

The objectives of the study include:

- To standardise duplex PCR for detection of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* from footrot lesions of sheep and goats
- To establish the association of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in causing footrot in sheep and goats
- To characterize the *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum* from the footrot samples

CHAPTER-II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Footrot

2.1.1 History

Early accounts of the footrot date back to the 15th century in Europe. The first recorded report of the disease was in 1791 in the French region, north of the pyrenees along the Gironde and lower medo rivers (Chabert *et al.*, 1791). Later, the disease was reported in France in 1813 and 1823, Italy and Germany in 1815 (De Gasparin, 1821).

Footrot was established in flocks of sheep in Maryland and Virginia by 1832, the disease was reported in Italy and in Germany in 1815, where it was introduced through the purchase of French Merinos. Footrot spreads to Great Britain and was reported in 1837, although it was hypothesised that it existed there well before that time (Youatt, 1837) and it was thought to be introduced into North America as early as 1797 via the importation of sheep from Europe to the regions of Ohio, Illinois (Mohler and Washburn, 1905).

Footrot was also introduced into Australia by importation of sheep. Anecdotal evidence suggests that the disease was introduced to India following the importation of Australian Corridale, Merino and Rambouillet sheep as part of the genetic improvement programme in 1970's (Mittal and Ghosh, 1979; Dixit *et al.*, 2006).

Footrot is introduced in India from the sheep of Australia during genetic improvement programme to upgrade wool quality in native Indian sheep breeds (Acharya, 1982).

Organisms that also cause footrot include *Staphylococcus* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *E. coli* and *A. pyogenes* (Hudson, 1982). Footrot is worldwide in distribution among countries having temperate climates which receive moderate to heavy rainfall (Stewart, 1989) and is caused by both aerobic and anaerobic organisms.

The *Fusobacterium* spp involved in animal and human infection are classified into biovar A and B and Strains of these biovars are reclassified as *F. necrophorum* subsp. *necrophorum* and subsp. *funduliforme* respectively (Shinjo *et al.*, 1991).

There are different variants of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* causing footrot, *Fusobacterium necrophorum* has four variants based on *lktA* gene viz; A,B,C and D (Bennett,1994). Footrot is a destructive hoof disease commonly seen in sheep and goats, and caused by the synergistic action of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* (whittier, 2005).

Aerobic organisms including *Staphylococcus* spp, *Streptococcus* spp, *E. coli* and *A. pyogenes* cannot initiate footrot (Hudson, 1982). They are involved in increasing the severity and incidence of footrot lesions caused by *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* (Currin *et al.*, 2009).

2.2 Other bacterial species implicated in footrot

Footrot is considered by many to be a polymicrobial disease even though the aetiology is attributed to *D. nodosus*. *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and *Treponema* spp. have been found in footrot lesions, (Beveridge, 1941., Egerton *et al.*, 1969; Roberts and Egerton, 1969;) of which *F. necrophorum* is perhaps the most studied and debated. Indeed, many bacterial genera reside in the interdigital skin of the ovine foot, differences in variety and quantity as they relate to clinical condition have been reported by Calvo-Bado *et al.*, (2011).

2.3 Reservoirs

The major reservoir of ovine footrot consists of sheep that are either subclinically or chronically infected with *D. nodosus*. Subclinical carriers can harbour the bacterium in the interdigital skin without showing any clinical signs of the disease. Chronic carriers are sheep that have not fully recovered after treatment or that have been affected by footrot for a long time. In both cases, new horn can be formed over bacteria that have remained within the foot. These encapsulated bacteria can survive for several years. Goats are as equally susceptible to footrot as sheep. Initially, cattle were considered unlikely potential reservoirs (Beveridge, 1941).

Dichelobacter nodosus has been isolated from other ruminants including goats (Claxton and O'Grady, 1986), cattle (Egerton and Parsonson, 1966), deer (Skerman, 1983) and were later thought only capable of harbouring benign *D. nodosus* (Wilkinson *et al.*, 1970). More recent research, had shown that cattle could be infected with virulent *D. nodosus* for a long time (Knappe-Poindecker *et al.*, 2014a). Virulent *D. nodosus* isolated from cattle was to induce severe disease in lambs under experimental conditions (Knappe-Poindecker *et al.*, 2014b). In turn, both benign and virulent strains of *D. nodosus* isolated from sheep had been successfully transferred to cattle, to induce interdigital dermatitis (Knappe-Poindecker *et al.*, 2015).

Survival of *D. nodosus* in the environment, i.e. outside of its host and niche is believed to be limited, but recent *in vitro* studies had shown that the bacterium could survive upto 40 days in soil (Enlund, 2010, Cederlöf *et al.*, 2013, Muzafar *et al.*, 2016).

2.4 Age and Sex Susceptibility

All age groups and both the sexes of sheep were found susceptible to footrot (Emery *et al.*, 1985). Younger sheep were generally more susceptible than older sheep (Seaman and Evers, 2006).

2.5 Epidemiology

2.5.1 Geographical distribution

Footrot has a world-wide distribution and has been reported from countries including Australia (Beveridge 1941), Holland (Toussaint and Cornelisse, 1971) Oregon (Schmitz and Gradin 1980), Spain (Piriz *et al.*, 1990) France (Popoff 1991), Denmark (Jessen *et al.*, 1993), United States (Gradin 1993), Nepal (Egerton *et al.*, 1994; Ghimire *et al.*, 1998), Britain (Naylor *et al.*, 1998), Canada (Olson *et al.*, 1998), , Malaysia (Zakaria *et al.*, 1998), New Zealand (Zhou and Hickford, 2000), Portugal (Jiminez *et al.*, 2003), India (Wani *et al.*, 2004).

Based on clinical symptoms, footrot had been reported from Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Andhra Pradesh. First confirmed outbreak of footrot in Andhra Pradesh was reported by Sreenivasulu *et al.*, (2013).

2.6 Environmental Factors

Warm, wet weather has been reported to be required for footrot outbreaks to occur. Several hypotheses have been proposed for the possible mechanisms by which footrot can be modulated by this warm, wet weather. Consistent rainfall over several weeks seems to be favourable for a footrot outbreak (Graham and Egerton, 1968).

The warm wet weather induce physical changes to the hoof that make it more vulnerable to attack (Graham and Egerton, 1968), or other unknown factors that increase the risk that a sheep will develop footrot.

2.7 Economic Losses

Footrot results in poor feed intake, reduction in the strength of the wool and in worst cases death from a combination of starvation, thirst, and other systemic bacterial infection leading to recumbency (Stewart, 1989). It has a significant negative effect on bodyweight and wool production of sheep (Marshall *et al.*, 1991).

2.8 Field diagnosis and clinical expression of Footrot

The provided five-point ordinal categories is used for visual diagnosis of footrot in sheep and to study its epidemiology and control before which damage to the epithelium of the interdigital skin is a prerequisite for the initiation of disease (Beveridge, 1941). It is characterized by two different clinical presentations, interdigital dermatitis (ID) and under-running footrot. Interdigital dermatitis is an initial inflammation of the interdigital skin where the superficial epidermal layers are inflamed, damaged and slough off irregularly and it may develop into under-running footrot, which is characterised by the separation of the hoof horn from the sensitive underlying tissue (Beveridge, 1941, Egerton *et al.*, 1969).

2.9 Control Measures

Designing of effective footrot eradication programme with a combination of various methods which include strict quarantine, culling, and vaccination along with effective regulatory support with conscientious farmer involvement helps in controlling footrot (Whittington *et al.*, 2004). Improved farm management practices, reducing stocking rates to decrease transmission, not following hoof paring, using

improved vaccination technologies and increasing the sheep's resistance to footrot by genetic selection, and these programme should include sustained long term control strategies in areas where climate favours transmission (Green and George, 2008).

There are several different medications namely, zinc sulphate(10%), and copper sulphate(10%) that can be applied to the hoof that are helpful in controlling foot rot (Dee whitter 2009).

Better strategies and tools were developed for the control and management of footrot that included new genetic testing and selective breeding tools which would create stock that gets less affected (Bennett *et al.* , 2010).

2.10 Prevalence of *d. nodosus* and *f. necrophorum* associated footrot

Detection of both *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* had been shown to be highly associated with under-running footrot in sheep and was showed that *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* occurred together at a significantly higher rate which suggested that they both might be involved in causing footrot. (Bennett *et al.*, 2009).

Both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* are together required for the disease manifestation and showed a close relation in causing footrot with their association (Farooq *et al.*, 2015). In a study conducted by Frosth *et al* (2015) the proportion of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* were more commonly found in association in flocks feet with footrot lesions than without lesions by using Real time PCR .

Vinod *et al*, (2016) reported combined prevalence of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in causing footrot in sheep and goats and concluded that both the organisms are to be considered for control and management of the disease. Presence

of both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in the same tissue samples was significantly higher in footrot compared with healthy feet (Maboni *et al.*, 2016).

2.10.1 The Genetics Of Footrot Resistance In Sheep

It had been observed that some breeds and lines of sheep were vulnerable or resistant to footrot (Emery *et al.*, 1984, Skerman and Moorhouse 1987), suggesting that footrot resistance is a heritable trait. Footrot resistance has also been linked to variation in the Major Histocompatibility Complex (MHC) genes (Outteridge *et al.*, 1989, Litchfield *et al.* 1993; Escayg *et al.*, 1997). In New Zealand, testing of the ovine MHC-DQA2 gene is used to identify particularly vulnerable sheep within a population and provide information for making selective breeding decisions (Bishop and Morris, 2007, Ennen *et al.*, 2009).

2.11 Etiological Agent

2.11.1 *Dichelobacter nodosus*

Dichelobacter is formerly known as *Bacteroides*. It is a pathogenic, anaerobic, non-spore-forming Gram-negative bacteria. It causes footrot in sheep, along with other bacteria and it is an obligate anaerobe of the family *Cardiobacteriaceae* (Dewhirst *et al.*, 1990). *Dichelobacter nodosus* has been found in footrot lesions in sheep (Beveridge 1941), goats (Beveridge 1983, Claxton and O'Grady 1986; Wani *et al.*, 2007), cattle (Egerton and Parsonson 1966), pigs (Piriz *et al.*, 1996), deer (Skerman, 1983) and some wild ungulates such as ibexes and mouflons (Belloy *et al.*, 2007).

2.11.1.1 Isolation of *D. nodosus*

The organism appears to have nutritional requirements which are not satisfied by normal laboratory media but which may be met partially by incorporation of Horse serum (Beveridge, 1941). Thomas (1958) eventually obtained consistent growth of cultures on a serum free agar medium supplemented with finely ground horn from sheep hooves.

This was followed by demonstration of the typical cellular morphology in Gram stained smears (Beveridge, 1941).

Hoof powder provides significant amounts of keratin that supplies arginine essential for growth of

D. nodosus. A particle free medium, called TAS (Trypticase-Arginine-Serine) for growth and isolation of the organism was described (Skerman, 1975).

The isolation of *D. nodosus* is an extremely difficult and time consuming process, partially because of its fastidious nature and also due to the presence of the large number of the different bacteria in footrot (Gradin and Schmitz, 1977). Depiazzi *et al.* (1990) modified TAS agar by incorporating cysteine as a reducing agent. La Fontanie and Rood, (1996) cultivated *D. nodosus* on Eugon agar and Eugon broth.

Dichelobacter nodosus isolates were cultured for three to four days on hoof agar, Eugon additional agar (2%-4%), yeast extract (2%) and defibrinated sheep blood (5%) were added to enhance certain features of *D. nodosus*. Streaked plates were incubated in anaerobic jars (BBL) at 37°C in 10% H₂, 10% CO₂, 80% N₂ and the catalysed with aluminum-palladium pellets (Cagatay and Hickford, 2006).

Culture of *D. nodosus* was performed using hoof agar (HA) under anaerobic conditions (AnaeroGen, Oxoid Ltd., UK) at 37°C. Primary cultures were made on 4% HA (1% proteose peptone, 0.5% NaCl, 0.4% beef extract, 0.1% yeast extract, finely ground ovine hoof horn, 4% bacto agar (Moore *et al.*, 2005).

Liquid cultures of *D. nodosus* (required for virulence testing) were prepared using TAS broth (Skerman, 1975; Depiazzi and Richards, 1985), modified to contain 1.5% trypticase peptone, 0.5% beef extract, 0.2% yeast extract, 0.5% proteose peptone, 0.5% L-arginine HCl and 0.15% DL-serine, the final pH was 7.8 (Moore *et al.*, 2005).

For isolation of *D. nodosus*, soil samples were cultured on 4% TASH plates (trypticase arginine serine hoof powder) and incubated anaerobically (80% N₂, 10% CO₂ and 10% H₂) at 37°C for four days. At day four, the colonies were visually evaluated and the presence or absence of suspected colonies recorded (Cederlöf *et al.*, 2013)

2.11.1.2 Colony Morphology

Dichelobacter nodosus is a strict anaerobe, and is a large Gram-negative rod with enlarged ends, measures 0.6–0.8 µm wide by 3–10 µm in length (Beveridge, 1941).

Coccoid forms may also be seen (Beveridge, 1941). Preliminary identification of *D. nodosus* is made after five days on the basis of the typical “ground-glass” colony morphology (Thorley, 1976; Skerman *et al.*, 1981).

2.11.1.3 Biochemical characteristics.

In general, biochemical tests are not being used to characterise *D. nodosus*. However, Buller *et al.*, (2014) reported that the *D. nodosus* is negative for

oxidase, catalase, urease, arginine decarboxylase (ADH), DNase, indole production, nitrate reduction, starch hydrolysis, aesculin hydrolysis and fermentation of glucose and sorbitol . Whereas it is positive for ornithine decarboxylase and H₂S production. Proteolytic activity is reported on media containing gelatin, casein and albumin (Buller *et al.*, 2014).

2.11.1.4 Serogrouping

Based on surface (K) antigen, Thorley (1976) reported that M-serotype was the third most common serotype in United Kingdom now known to be fimbriae.

Claxton *et al.*, (1983) showed that the highest proportion of *D. nodosus* strains isolated and identified in Australia belonged to serogroup B (2.82%). Hindmarsh and Fraser (1985) reported a predominant prevalence of serogroup B (40.4%) in Great Britain. Claxton and Grady (1986) classified *D. nodosus* isolates obtained from Australian sheep into nine (A-I) serogroups and 18 serotypes.

Thorley and Day (1986) while investigating the distribution of *D. nodosus* serogroups in France, The Netherlands, Belgium, Italy, Sicily and Sardinia, reported that majority of the strains belonged to serogroup H (32.7%), followed by D (14.4%) and C (13.5%). Only 4-5% of the strains belonged to serogroup A. Kingsley *et al.*, (1986) studied the distribution of *D. nodosus* serogroups B (40.3%), followed by H (26.5%) and D (10.9%) in New Zealand and Great Britain. The prevalence of *D. nodosus* serotype M in Australia and New Zealand was first revealed by Chetwin *et al.*, (1991) before recognition of M-serotype, all were serotyped as F-serotype. Out of total number of F- isolates retyped, 31% of the Australian isolates and 50% of New Zealand isolates were typed as M-serotype. M-serotype is one of the major serotypes present in Australia and New Zealand have now been reported from other countries.

Dichelobacter nodosus serogroup A, B, C, G and M have been reported from South Africa, (Coetzer *et al.*, 1994), Nepal (Ghimire *et al.*, 1996), (Ghimire *et al.*, 1998), Spain (Hurtado *et al.*, 1998), U.S.A (John *et al.*, 1999) and New Zealand (Zhou and Hickford, 2000).

Class I contains the majority of the *D. nodosus* serogroups A, B, C, E, F, G, I and M – whereas class II contains only serogroups D and H (Ghimire *et al.*, 1998). Wani *et al.*, (2004 and 2007) and Hussain *et al.*, (2009) reported the presence of B, E, and I sero- groups from Jammu and Kashmir, India.

Serogroups A, B, C, E, F, I and H were reported from southern India among them B was the most frequent at 50.4%, I is about 29.3%, and A is 14% (Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013; Vinod *et al.*, 2016).

2.11.1.5 The virulence factors of *D. nodosus*

Dichelobacter nodosus strains have a wide range of virulence with several virulence factors. These include fimbriae. *Dichelobacter nodosus* carries fimbriae which help in colonisation (Walker *et al.* 1973, Stewart 1973), and the ability to secrete thermo-stable proteases is other virulence factor (Thomas, 1962; Riffkin *et al.*, 1995) the occurrence of a variety of genetic elements with a postulated gene regulatory function were involved in virulence (Katz *et al.* 1991; Myers *et al.*, 2007).

2.11.1.6 Fimbriae

Variation within the fimbrial subunit gene, *fimA* is responsible for determining serotype and fimbriae have been used as the primary antigen in vaccines developed against *D. nodosus* (Egerton 1973, Stewart 1978, Liardet *et al.*, 1989).

Fimbriae are known to be glycosylated in some strains of *D. nodosus* (Cagatay and Hickford, 2008) and several functions of the type IV fimbriae have been described. These include: allowing bacterial binding to epithelial cells (Kennan *et al.*, 2001, Parker *et al.*, 2006), having a role in twitching motility (Kennan *et al.*, 2001, Parker *et al.*, 2006), facilitating the ability to take up extra-cellular DNA (Kennan *et al.*, 2001, Han *et al.*, 2007) and a role in a secretion system in *D. nodosus* to export proteases from the bacterial cytoplasm (Kennan *et al.*, 2001, Parker *et al.*, 2006, Han *et al.*, 2007, Myers *et al.*, 2007).

The genome of *D. nodosus* carries 21 fimbrial biogenesis genes and the isolates typically express type IV polar fimbriae (Myers *et al.*, 2007).

2.11.1.7 Proteases

The proteases of *D. nodosus* were able to hydrolyse keratin (Thomas, 1964) and could be used to predict the virulence of an isolate (Egerton and Parsonson, 1969).

Dichelobacter nodosus carried three protease genes and the activities of the secreted proteases of *D. nodosus* are important during the development of footrot (Thomas, 1962; Egerton and Parsonson, 1969; Riffkin *et al.*, 1995; Myers *et al.*, 2007).

This has led to the measurement of protease stability as a predictor of the virulence of *D. nodosus* strains *in vitro*, since it was highly associated ($P < 0.001$) with the "virulent" classification of an individual *D. nodosus* strain (Egerton and Parsonson, 1969). The genes encoding these proteases have been found on a putative "genomic island" in *D. nodosus*, suggesting an extra-chromosomal source, such as from a horizontal gene-transfer event (Myers *et al.*, 2007).

2.11.1.8 Elastases

Stewart (1979) explained the role of *D. nodosus* proteases elastolytic activity, in digesting horn and separation of the hoof from the soft tissue. Liu *et al.*, (1994) reported that the results of elastase test appeared to be slightly closer to those of the dot blot when compared with gelatin gel test. The results of elastase test and gelatin test were dependent on factors that affect the bacterial growth and metabolism. Links and Morris (1996) performed gelatin gel test and elastase test on 4296 isolates of *D. nodosus* derived from 457 outbreaks in New South Wales and reported the high levels of repeatability and recommended to use elastase test where a graded assessment of protease activity is desired.

Kennan *et al.*, (2011) studied the mutants of extracellular protease genes and reported that *AprV2* was one of the major stable thermostable protease responsible for extracellular protease activity and reported to be associated with virulence. Gilhuus *et al.*, (2013) reported very good agreement between the elastase test and gelatin gel test and preferred gelatin gel test over elastase because of shorter incubation period.

2.11.1.9 The *fim A* gene

Class I fimbriae included those of serogroups A, B, C, E, F, G and I, while class II contained serogroups D and H. Elleman (1988) suggested that the two sets of fimbriae are also distinguished by their disulphide loop profile.

The fimbriae of *D. nodosus* were classified as type IV because of their highly conserved amino-terminal region, polar location, association with twitching motility, and the presence of an N-methyl phenylalanine residue as the N-terminal amino acid (Strom and Lory, 1993).

Mattick *et al.*, (1991) reported that based on the DNA sequences, fimbriae of *D. nodosus* are classified into two broad classes. The authors opined that both the classes contained an identical leader sequence and hydrophobic amino terminal region up to residue 18 and the sequence homology was highly conserved to residue 32.

Both class I and class II fimbrial gene regions are flanked by the *aroA* gene, upstream and the *clpB* gene, downstream. Hobbs *et al.*, (1991) reported that the proteins encoded by the *aroA* and the *clpB* genes are found in a number of bacteria that do not express type-IV fimbriae, it is unlikely that either is involved in fimbrial morphogenesis or function. Zhou and Hickford (2000) studied genetic recombination in the fimbrial genes by amplifying *fimA* gene by PCR and two novel amplicons were produced.

Type IV fimbriae had been shown to be essential for natural transformation in several bacterial species and is regarded as a major virulence factor, as they are highly immunogenic. The simplest and most likely explanation for these results is that colonisation of the interdigital skin and inactivation of the encoding gene, *fimA*, by allelic exchange produced mutants that did not exhibit twitching motility, had lower levels of extracellular protease and did not cause infection when inoculated into sheep hoof (Kennan *et al.*, 2001).

Zhou and Hickford (2000) carried out molecular analysis of *fimA* gene and revealed that variation existed at both amino acid and nucleotide level. Nucleotide deletions or insertions were not only responsible for the small number of gaps introduced to align *fimA* sequences, but can also cause frame shifts for the downstream sequence.

Sequencing of the novel PCR products suggested recombination between two different serotypes. Kennan *et al.*, (2003) demonstrated the ability of *D. nodosus* to undergo natural transformation and homologous transformation was identified when a serogroup I strain was seroconverted to a serogroup G strain *in vitro*.

Vinod *et al.*, (2015) performed phylogenetic analysis of *fimA* gene from south Indian isolates of *D. nodosus* serogroup B and found a high genetic similarity of the south Indian isolates with serotype B1.

2.11.1.10 Immunology of *D. nodosus*

Dichelobacter nodosus infection of the epidermis causes an immune response, although it is not long-lasting (Egerton and Roberts, 1971). Understanding the immune response is important in many aspects, for example natural resistance and vaccine development, both of which can be used to control disease. Natural resistance to footrot differs between sheep breeds (Emery *et al.*, 1984).

British breeds are more resistant whereas merinos are more susceptible (Emery *et al.*, 1984). Footrot resistance is associated with variation in the MHC II (Escayg *et al.*, 1997). In 1969, the first footrot vaccine was developed and used in research (Egerton, 1970). It was based on *D. nodosus* whole cells, but later purified fimbriae were shown to be equally effective (Egerton *et al.*, 1987; Every & Skerman, 1982). Several different vaccines against footrot have been developed since then, consisting of either whole cells or purified fimbriae (Dhungyel *et al.*, 2014). Footvax contains many different serogroups (nine of ten, A-I), since immunity is serogroup-specific. An efficient vaccine against all *D. nodosus* serogroups would be ideal since multiple serogroups can be present within a flock (Claxton *et al.*, 1983).

Furthermore, *D.nodosus* might seroconvert (Kennan *et al.*, 2003). Cross-protective antigens have been identified by reverse vaccinology (Myers *et al.*, 2007).

2.11.2 *Fusobacterium necrophorum*

Fusobacterium necrophorum is an obligate anaerobe believed to be a member of the normal flora of the human oro-pharyngeal and urogenital tract. It has been associated with deep-seated infections and was first described in 1936 by Lemierre, a French microbiologist. It was classified into three biovars as A, B, and C according to hemagglutinating and haemolytic activities (Fievez, 1963). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* is a Gram-negative anaerobic pleomorphic and nonspore forming bacterium which is more sensitive to oxygen than *D. nodosus* (Farooq *et al.*, 2018).

The *F. necrophorum* is more frequently encountered in animal infection, while clinical isolates from human infections have characteristics of subsp. *fundiliforme*. The leukotoxin (lktA) a secreted protein is a major virulence factor in the two subspecies *Fusobacterium necrophorum* subsp. *necrophorum* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* subsp. *fundiliforme* (Tan *et al.*, 1992; Amoako *et al.*, 1993).

The subsp. *necrophorum* is more virulent because of the presence and increased production of potent virulence factors such as leukotoxin, lipopolysaccharide, and hemagglutinin. (Amit Kumar *et al.*, 2013).

2.11.2.1 ISOLATION

Fusobacterium spp are frequently isolated from clinically significant anaerobic infections using *Fusobacterium* egg yolk agar (FEA), which contains josamycin, vancomycin, and neomycin and is highly selective for *Fusobacterium* species and differential for *F. necrophorum* (Morgenstein *et al.*, 1981), for isolating on surfaces of enriched brain-heart infusion blood agar (BHIBA). Plates that contained

5% haemolysed bovine blood was used and were incubated at 37°C in an atmosphere of 90% H₂, and 10% CO₂ for three to five days (Emery *et al.*, 1985).

Fusobacterium necrophorum did not grow well on plain blood agar. So, an additional fastidious anaerobic blood agar (FAA) plate containing neomycin (100 mg/L) was inoculated and a 30 µg vancomycin disc was placed at the junction of the second and third streaks. (Amess *et al.*, 2007).

These organisms could be grown on Columbia agar plates supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood, 100 mg/L neomycin, 5 mg/L vancomycin and 1 mg/L erythromycin, and incubated anaerobically for three days at 37°C (Witte *et al.*, 2016).

2.12.2 Colony Morphology

On egg yolk agar, β-haemolytic strains were lipase positive and α-haemolytic (or) nonhaemolytic strains were lipase negative, no lecithin was produced. Filamentous forms are seen usually in young cultures and bacilli in older cultures. Surface colonies on blood agar are 1–2 mm in diameter; circular with scalloped to erose edges, convex to umbonate, often with bumpy, ridged, or uneven surface. The smell of butyric acid and fluorescence of a yellow/green colour under ultraviolet light at 365 nm can be seen and is used for identification of mixed cultures (Amess *et al.*, 2007).

Most strains produce either α- or β-haemolysis on rabbit blood agar. In general, the β-hemolytic strains are lipase positive (on egg yolk agar), and the α-haemolytic or non-haemolytic strains are lipase negative. (James and whittman, 2010).

2.12.3 Virulence factors of *F. necrophorum*

The strategies carried by the *F. necrophorum* to establish its virulence are endotoxin, leukotoxin, haemagglutinin, capsule, adhesins, platelet aggregation factor, and certain extracellular enzymes among them Endotoxin and leukotoxin are more important than other toxins in overcoming the host's defence mechanisms to establish the infection (Tan *et al.*, 1996).

2.12.4 Endotoxin

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) also causes erythema and oedema in rabbit skin (Berg and Scanlan, 1982), and hepatic degeneration and necrosis in mice and it is lethal to chicken embryos, mice, and rabbits, causes localised and generalised Schwartzman reactions and induces a biphasic pyrogenic response in rabbits (Inoue *et al.*, 1985; Nakajima *et al.*, 1988). The Outer membrane of *F. necrophorum* as like other Gram-negative bacteria contains endotoxic LPS and its chemical composition is variable and dependent on subspecies, and strains Okahashi *et al.*, 1988).

2.12.5 Haemolysin

The strains of biovar A are more pathogenic than those of biovar B (Shinjo, 1983). The haemolytic activity of *F. necrophorum* has been reported in both the culture supernatant and cell fraction (Abe *et al.*, 1979; Kanoe *et al.*, 1984, Amoako *et al.*, 1994, Tan *et al.*, 1994).

2.12.6 Leukotoxin

Leukotoxic activity of *F. necrophorum* was demonstrated by leukocyte migration inhibition and the cells were destroyed and more infective than a non-leukotoxin-producing strain in causing abscesses in mice (Roberts, 1967). The subsp. *necrophorum* produced about 18 times more leukotoxin than subsp. *funduliforme*.

Several investigators have reported that subsp. *necrophorum* produces more leukotoxin than subsp. *fundiliforme* (Scanlan *et al.*, 1982, 1986). The difference in toxin production might account for the difference in virulence between the two subspecies (Shinjo *et al.*, 1981; Berg and Scanlan, 1982). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* leukotoxin is a soluble, proteinaceous and heat-labile exotoxin with specificity for ruminant neutrophils (Coyle-Dennis and Lauerman, 1978; Emery *et al.*, 1986; Kanoe *et al.*, 1986; Tan *et al.*, 1994).

2.12.7 Leukotoxin Gene

The *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum* is composed of 9723 bp, encoding 3240 amino acids. The *lktA* protein is a high molecular weight, secreted protein, and its predicted molecular weight is 33,5860 Kd (Tan *et al.*, 1994).

The *lktA* protein of *F. necrophorum* was considered to be a major virulence factor in the course of footrot due to the killing effect on neutrophils of ruminant (Tan *et al.*, 1996; Narayanan *et al.*, 2001).

Two immunodominant regions, BSBSE (1 bp–1112 bp) and SH (5623 bp–7492 bp), were identified with better protective effects in mice against infection of *F. necrophorum* strain A25 (Narayanan *et al.*, 2003).

The full length of the *lktA* gene was truncated into five presenters of overlapping sequences for expression analysis for determination of *lktA* gene (Narayanan *et al.*, 2001). The leukotoxin gene (*lktA*) in subsp. *necrophorum* is encoded by the tricistronic *lktBAC* operon (Narayanan *et al.*, 2001). The first determinant *lktB* consists of 551 codons yielding a protein with a molecular weight of 62,981 Kd. The protein peptide is (MFHCKKELKTFVFFMLILSCPNI) at N-terminus of the protein indicating the outer membrane protein in *F. necrophorum* and

LktB has a conserved domain with the FhaC protein which determines the possibility of LktB protein may be responsible for the secretion LktA protein by this Gram-negative bacterium (Oelke *et al.*, 2005).

Downstream of the leukotoxin determinant is lktC. The ATG start codon for lktC overlaps the TGA stop codon of lktA. This gene encodes a predicted protein of 145 amino acids with a molecular weight of 17,150 Kd. The protein does not show significant sequence similarity to proteins currently in the NCBI databases. There is no ORF immediately downstream of the lktC determinant (the next ORF is 138 bp away) suggesting that lktC is the terminal gene in the operon. The partial downstream ORF sequence does not display significant sequence similarity to any known determinant (Oelke *et al.*, 2005).

These properties make the lktA protein a suitable candidate for genetic engineering of vaccines and diagnostic reagents. Although lktA protein was a suitable candidate for genetic engineering of vaccines, Preparation of the protein *in vitro* was very difficult according to the current genetic engineering technique. Out of the five recombinant proteins, PL1, PL3 and PL4 had better protective effects in mice. Further analysis found that the immunodominant PL1 (1 bp–523 bp) and PL4 (5645 bp–6632 bp) reported here were more accurate than the immunodominant BSBSE (1 bp –1112 bp) and SH (5623 bp –7492 bp) reported by (Narayanan *et al.*, 2002). In addition, the immunodominant PL3 (3957 bp – 6080 bp) reported in this study was a novel immunodominant region on lktA protein of *F. necrophorum* (Sun *et al.*, 2009).

The last promoter containing fragment in subsp *necrophorum* is of 548 bp (Zhang *et al.*, 2006). The protein encoded by the lktA is of ~336 kDa and the determinant is ~10 kb where the lac operon of *F.necrophrum* subsp *necrophorum* and

subsp *fundiliforme* has an organization, first gene *lktB* is 650 bp in size, the structural gene *lktA* is 9,732 bp and the last gene *lktC* is 438 bp in size, respectively (Tadepalli, 2007). The varying sizes were due to differences in two poly-A stretches around 230 bp and 190 bp from the start codon of the *lktB* open reading frame (ORF). Homopolymeric tract variations had previously been reported to affect gene expression levels and therefore activity in other bacteria (Scholz *et al.*, 2016).

The *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum* is composed of 9723 bp, encoding 3240 amino acids. The *lktA* protein is a high molecular weight, secreted protein, and its predicted molecular weight is 33, 5860 Kd (Tan *et al.*, 1994).

2.13 Pathogenesis of Footrot

Dichelobacter nodosus is the causative agent of interdigital dermatitis and underrunning footrot (Beveridge, 1941). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* establishes infection by the development of interdigital dermatitis (Parsonson *et al.*, 1967) leading to the detachment due to protease enzyme activity by *D. nodosus* (Roberts, 1967; Egerton *et al.*, 1969). Initially, *D. nodosus* appears to invade the epidermal matrix and cause hoof separation, providing a necessary environment where *F. necrophorum* can flourish (Egerton *et al.*, 1969). Footrot organisms displays a wide range of virulence and the disease has been categorized as virulent, benign or intermediate (Stewart *et al.*, 1986).

Systemic infections in footrot is characterised by embolic metastatic inflammations formed in major vital organs such as liver, lungs, brain, heart, and kidneys as a result of vasculitis formed in the veins in the inflamed region, where the agents are spread by the bloodstream (Alibasoglu and Yesildere, 1988).

In cattle, *F. necrophorum* causes diphtheria (Jang and Hirsh, 1994). Other conditions reported by the involvement of *F. necrophorum* are pharyngo tonsillitis, pharyngitis, parotitis, dental abscesses and middle ear infections including mastoiditis (Brook, 1994) hepatic and abdominal abscesses (Tan *et al.*, 1996), in calves. The pathogenesis of footrot is multifactorial and complex (Billington *et al.*, 1996). In humans, it causes Lemierre's syndrome that mainly affects young and healthy persons (Kristensen and Prag, 2000). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* are essential for the invasion of the epidermal matrix of the hoof and neither bacterial species alone will cause a footrot lesion (Abbott and Lewis, 2005). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* is present as a primary or secondary opportunistic pathogen in numerous necrotic disease conditions generally termed necrobacillosis in humans, domestic and wild animals (Nagaraja *et al.*, 2005).

Benign strains of *D. nodosus* cause interdigital skin inflammation, which is impossible to distinguish clinically from interdigital dermatitis caused by *F. necrophorum*, spontaneous regression occurs even in the most affected animals after normalisation of the environmental conditions (Green and George, 2008). The progression of the disease involves hoof horn separation mainly by *D. nodosus* (Rebecca *et al.*, 2014), *D. nodosus* plays the primary role in disease pathogenesis while *F. necrophorum* plays a secondary role (Luci *et al.*, 2014).

In small pen trials, histological and challenge studies showed that *F. necrophorum* pre-disposed sheep to footrot (Egerton *et al.*, 1969; Roberts and Egerton, 1969). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* like cells were seen to invade the epidermis several days before a *D. nodosus* infection occurred and *F. necrophorum* could be seen in the leading edge of the newly developing footrot lesions (Egerton *et al.*, 1969).

Footrot was able to be induced by injection of cultures of both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* together into the inter-digital skin, but neither bacterium was able to induce footrot consistently when injected alone (Roberts and Egerton, 1969).

Vaccination against *F. necrophorum* was attempted to control footrot, but *F. necrophorum* antigens were found to generate poor immune responses in sheep and a little protective effect (Egerton and Roberts, 1971). *Fusobacterium necrophorum* was also involved in the invasion of tissue during ovine interdigital dermatitis (footrot or scald) and histological and bacteriological studies suggested that it could be acting as a causative agent (Parsonson *et al.*, 1967).

A foot abscess model had been demonstrated where *F. necrophorum* biovar AB cultures were able to induce foot abscesses if the feet were first devitalised with liquid nitrogen and the interdigital skin injected with *F. necrophorum* biovar AB (Corner *et al.*, 1996). Maboni *et al.*, (2016) and others also reported increased prevalence and load of *F. necrophorum*, but only in under-running footrot and *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* were almost exclusively observed in the epidermis, at all stages of the disease. This might partly explained the relatively low efficacy and duration of protection of existing vaccines, which use systemic antibody production rather than protection in the epidermis (Witcomb *et al.*, 2015).

2.14 Molecular detection of *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* in Footrot samples

2.14.1 Fluorescence *in situ* hybridization

Developments in molecular methods had greatly contributed for the detection of various pathogens as early as possible with these techniques involving the typical colony and microscopic morphology as well as the biochemical differentiation by the API systems (BioMerieux, Nurtigen, Germany) are often used for presumptive

identification of *Fusobacterium* spp. (Tanner *et al.*, 1985; Summanen and Jousimies Somer, 1988; Moore *et al.*, 1994; Tanner *et al.*, 1994).

The identification of *Fusobacterium* spp. is complicated by their slow growth rate and frequently occurring concomitant flora with the application of Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) assay was proved to be a promising method that might significantly accelerate and improve the identification of the most frequently isolated species of *F. nucleatum* and *F. necrophorum*, in a routine laboratory (Sigge *et al.*, 2007).

In FISH, probes were used to study for determining the load and localisation of these protocols were tested empirically both *in vitro* and on tissue biopsies spiked with *D. nodosus* or *F. necrophorum* cells to conclude their association and postulated that this could be due to the higher sensitivity of the qPCR assays compared (FISH), which was supported by the increased detection frequency of amplicons from the interdigital skin. (Witcomb *et al.*, 2015).

2.14.2 PCR for detection of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*

Amplification of the fimbrial gene sequence of *D. nodosus* had been identified and grouped by specific primers which allow the PCR amplification of specific genes that are extracted from pure colonies by the purification of portions of the variable region of the fimbrial cells which are present in the gene (John *et al.*, 1990).

Polymerase chain reaction for detection of 16SrRNA gene of *D. nodosus* was employed by La Fontaine *et al* (1993). Later PCR approach would improve the accuracy in identifying specific serogroups, and reveal new emerging groups based on nucleotide base changes within the fimbrial gene (John *et al.*, 1999).

Though four different variants of *F. necrophorum* were present in footrot lesions, there was quite no evidence of mixed-strain infection for *F. necrophorum* in sheep, goats and cattle. This is in contrast to *D. nodosus*, for which mixed-strain infections were common (Zhou and Hickford, 2000) and there might be up to seven strains present on a single hoof (Zhou and Hickford, 2001). For the ITS amplification, a new eubacterial universal primer pair was designed and used (Conrads *et al.*, 2002). Multiplex PCR with nine (A–I) serogroup-specific primers was used for serogrouping the *D. nodosus* isolates (Dhungyel *et al.*, 2002).

The PCR amplicons of *F. necrophorum* subsp. *necrophorum* *lktA* sequence exhibited polymorphism upon SSCP analysis and in total four unique patterns could be detected (Zhou *et al.*, 2009). Failure to detect *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* by PCR on the surface of all sheep hooves infected with under-running footrot, does not eliminate *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* as causative agents of footrot, especially considering their anaerobic nature (Bennett *et al.*, 2009).

The duplex PCR was proved to be a quick method for rapid identification of *F. necrophorum* isolates with detectable *lktA* gene since there is an ongoing debate on the presence of this gene in all *F. necrophorum* isolates (Ludlam *et al.*, 2009; Bennett *et al.*, 2010).

Duplex PCR designed for characterisation of *F. necrophorum* species includes primers for the target regions of RNA polymerase β subunit (*Rpo B*), and *lktA* gene. Cycliplex PCR comprising primer target regions Gyrase β subunit (*Gyr B*), haemagglutinin related protein (*Wlf*), *lktA* gene and *Fusobacterium* genus 16S rDNA (*Fuso*) 610 bp respectively (Antiabong *et al.*, 2013).

Various researchers targeted 16S rRNA gene in *D. nodosus* and *lktA* gene in *F. necrophorum* from footrot lesions for PCR based diagnosis in India (Wani *et al.*, 2004, Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013, Uttar Pradesh, Nayakwadi *et al.*, 2014, Anton *et al.*, 2014, Vinod *et al.*, 2016).

2.14.3 Real-time PCR for *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* detection.

Fusobacterium necrophorum is considered to enhance disease severity through synergistic relationships with other pathogens (Brook and Walker, 1986; Tan *et al.*, 1996) and other Fusobacteria that are present in lesions and abscesses in many polymicrobial infections (Brook and Frazier, 1997; Brook, 2002; Hofstad 2006), to overcome the complexity of determining load of each organism quantitative PCR is approached (LA Calvo-Bado *et al.*, 2011).

Samples that were positive by the real-time PCR but were negative or had faint bands in the conventional PCR were positive for sequence analysis and the real-time PCR method which detected 8% more positive samples compared to the conventional PCR (Frosth *et al.*, 2012).

A competitive real-time PCR was developed based on allelic discrimination of the protease genes *aprV2* and *aprB2* of *D. nodosus* and this method allowed direct detection and differentiation of virulent and benign *D. nodosus* from interdigital skin swabs in a single test (Stäuble *et al.*, 2014).

Targets chosen for identification of *D. nodosus* is 61bp *rpoD* gene (RNA polymerase σ subunit) and 86 bp *rpoB* gene (RNA polymerase β subunit) for *F. necrophorum* in qPCR analysis (Witcomb *et al.*, 2014).

The new insights of colonisation studies of *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* using real-time PCR revealed that *D. nodosus* drives the early stages of footrot and *F. necrophorum* plays a role in the pathogenesis of footrot (Maboni *et al.*, 2016).

2.14.4 Multiple locus variable number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) schemes for *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*

The clonal complexes of the individual MLVA types are broadly supported by investigation of population structure analysis at the most hierarchical level. This indicated that there are seven independent populations of *D. nodosus* (Russell *et al.*, 2014).

Multiple locus variable number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) types of *D. nodosus* present in three clonal complexes in which India and Scandinavia were never present in the same clonal complex this suggests that isolates from these countries have different origins (Russell *et al.*, 2014).

For the improved understanding of reservoirs of *F. necrophorum* a sensitive, specific, stable and discriminatory MLVA typing scheme was developed and validated for both the isolates and community DNA samples from the sheep by Clifton *et al.*, (2018).

CHAPTER-III

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Collection of Data

Data were collected from the inspected flocks on prevalence of footrot, with symptoms and other associated risk factors observed during the outbreak from the sheep and goat of different districts in Andhra Pradesh.

A total of 81 flocks were inspected and 172 samples were collected from footrot suspected cases of sheep and goat. Eighty five gingival swab samples were also collected from healthy and affected sheep given in (Fig 1 and Fig 2).

Sheep and goats with symptoms of lameness, infectious dermatitis of the interdigital skin of with a grey scum, pungent and characteristic rotting smell were suspected for footrot.

Table no.1 Details of Samples collection

S.no	Name of the District	No. of flocks visited	Suspected cases of Footrot			Gingival swabs collected
			Sheep	Goat	Total	
1	Chittoor	35	52	32	84	60
2	Kadapa	6	12	8	20	5
3	Nellore	14	15	9	24	5
4	East Godavari	13	10	8	18	8
5	Ananthapur	13	14	12	26	9
	Total	81	103	69	172	85

3.2 Screening of Samples

All the samples were screened by standardised PCR protocol by La fontaine *et al*, (1993) and duplex PCR was designed and standardised in the department for detection of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. Gingival swabs were screened separately for *F. necrophorum* by PCR targeting LktA gene.

3.3 Glassware and Plasticware

The glassware and plasticware used in the study were procured from Borosil, Scott Duran and Tarsons. The sterile cotton swabs were procured from Hi media.

3.4 Biochemicals and enzymes

The following biochemicals either of molecular biology grade or analytical grade were used in the present study. Agarose, ethidium bromide, bromophenol blue and EDTA were obtained from Genei, Bangalore. Glycerol and other chemicals were procured from SRL, India. *Taq* DNA polymerase supplied by Genei, Bangalore was used for amplification of the template and deoxyribonucleotide triphosphate (dNTP) mix containing dATP, dGTP, dCTP and dTTP at a final concentration of 10 mM and MgCl₂ 15mM each were from Genei. Nuclease-free water was procured from Genei, Bangalore. Small aliquots of one millilitre were preserved at -20 °C.

3.5 DNA extraction

Swabs were suspended in 100 µl of sterile phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and the suspension was prepared by gentle vortexing for five minutes. The suspension was boiled for five minutes, cooled down on ice for 10 minutes and centrifuged at 10,000 g for one minute. The suspension was stored at -20 °C for further use. Two microlitre of the sample was used as template in PCR.

3.6 Polymerase Chain Reaction

3.6.1 Primers used for Uniplex and Duplex PCR

Primers used in the duplex PCR were 16S rRNA and *lktA*, where 16S rRNA primers starting at 67 and stop at 849 having an internal region of 783 bp described by (Dewhirst et al., 1990; La Fontaine *et al.*, 1993) were used *lktA* primers were designed for duplex PCR using Gene Runner 6.5 (Buquicchio, 2018) software.

3.6.2 Designing of *lktA* Primer

The *lktA* primers were designed from *lktA* full gene DQ672338.1 using Gene runner software version 6.5.51 Beta (Buquicchio, 2018), with the primer's specificity is checked by alignment using the MEGA software version 7.0.26 (Kumar *et al.*, 2016), with the start codon is at 109th position and the stop codon at 621th position on *lktA* full gene having an amplification region of 512 bp.

Table no 2. Details of 16S rRNA and *lktA* oligonucleotide primers

Primer	Primer Sequence	M.W (kd)	GC%	Tm °C	Primer length (bp)	Product size (bp)
16SrRNA	F-CGGGGTTATGTAGCTTGC	5561.7	56	55.6	18	783
	R-TCGGTACCGAGTATTTCTACCCAACACCT	8772.8	56	48.3	29	
<i>lktA</i>	F- AATGATACAATCGCCGCGAC	6095.0	45	49.7	20	500
	R- ATCCGCCGCATATAAACCGA	6055	52.6	51.1	19	

3.6.3 Protocol for preparation of PCR reaction mixture

The following reagents were added carefully.

3.6.4 PCR reaction mixture for 16SrRNA of *D. nodosus*

<i>Taq</i> buffer A(10X)	-	2.5 µl
MgCl ₂ (25mM)	-	1.0 µl
dNTP mix (10mM)	-	0.3 µl
Forward Primer 10p mol/µl	-	0.6 µl

Reverse Primer	10p mol/μl	-	0.6 μl
Taq DNA polymerase	(5U/μl)	-	0.3 μl
Template DNA		-	2.0 μl
Nuclease free water	-	-	17.7 μl
Total volume-			<u>25 μl</u>

Polymerase chain reaction was carried out in a Thermal cycler (Biorad C1000 Touch).

3.6.5 Amplification Temperatures for Detection of *D. nodosus* 16S rRNA

Initial Denaturation 94°C-2 min

Step-1 94°C-30 sec

Step-2 60°C-30 sec

Step-3 72°C-30 sec

Run for 5 cycles

Step-4 94°C-30 sec

Step-5 58°C-30 sec

Step-6 72°C-30 sec

Run for 25 cycles

Step-7 72°C-4 min

Polymerase chain reaction test for detection and grouping of *D. nodosus* targeting 16S rRNA gene was conducted as per the standardized protocols. DNA from *D. nodosus* serogroup-I isolated in this laboratory and confirmed by sequencing of its *fimA* gene fragment served as positive control. The PCR products in two percent agarose gel were stained with ethidium bromide and the results were analyzed and documented using Gel Documentation system (Alpha Innotech, AlphaImager HP).

3.6.6 PCR reaction mixture for lktA gene of *F. necrophorum*

The following reagents were added carefully.

<i>Taq</i> buffer A(10X)	-	2.5 μ l
Mgcl ₂ (25mM)	-	0.5 μ l
dNTP mix (10mM)	-	0.3 μ l
Forward Primer10p mol/ μ l	-	0.25 μ l
Reverse Primer10p mol/ μ l	-	0.25 μ l
<i>Taq</i> DNA polymerase (5U/ μ l)	-	0.3 μ l
Template DNA	-	2 μ l
Nuclease-free water	-	17.7 μ l
Total volume		<u>25 μl</u>

The tubes were spinned for 10 seconds and PCR was carried out in a Thermal cycler (Biorad C1000 Touch).

3.6.7 PCR Amplification of lktA gene

Initial denaturation 94°C-2 min

Step-1 94°C-30 sec

Step-2 60°C-30 sec

Step-3 72°C-40 sec

Run for 35 cycles

Step-4 72°C-5 min

Polymerase chain Reaction for detection of *F. necrophorum* targeting the lktA gene was conducted as per the protocols standardized. Deoxyribo nucleic acids extracted from the swab samples were tested with known standard positive DNA obtained from UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK, London, United Kingdom with Ref no: Fn DSM 21784 and sterile distilled water served as negative control. The PCR

products in 1.5% agarose gel were stained with ethidium bromide and the results were analysed using gel documentation system (Alpha Innotech, AlphaImager HP) and photographed.

3.6.8 Duplex PCR design

Two sets of primers (La Fontaine *et al.*, 1993) were synthesized by Sigma Aldrich. The primer set of LktA amplifies a 512 bp starting at 109 and stopping at 621 region of the lktA gene, which is designed and used as a genetic marker for *F. necrophorum*. The primer set of 16S rRNA amplifies a 783 bp amplicon of the 16S rRNA. Duplex PCR using these two primer sets would accordingly produce the 783 bp amplicon for *D. nodosus*, and 512 bp amplicon in the case of *F. necrophorum*.

3.6.9 Positive DNA for standardisation of Duplex PCR

F. necrophorum DNA was provided by UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK, London, United Kingdom with Ref no: Fn DSM 21784. *Dichelobacter nodosus* DNA was prepared from stock cultures (serogroup I) maintained in this laboratory.

3.6.10 Dilutions of Primers and DNA for Standardisation of Duplex PCR

3.6.10.1 Primer's Dilution

To test the sensitivity of the primers different dilutions were made

Table no 3. Details of Primer dilutions for Duplex PCR

Serial dilutions	concentration of diluted primers(pmol/μl)	Volume of primers added for reaction (F+R) μl	Final concentrations of added Primers (F+R)pmol/μl
1:4	25	2.5	62.5
1:10	10	1	10
1:20	5	0.5	2.5
1:40	2.5	0.5	1.25

These primer dilutions are used accordingly in different individual PCR reactions to check their level of sensitivity in amplifying DNA. Specificity was determined by visualising the gene under U.V illuminator at 783 bp for 16S rRNA and 500 bp for *LktA* genes.

3.6.10.2 Dilutions of Template DNA for Duplex PCR

To evaluate level of low concentrations of DNA that can be detected by the specific primers at different concentrations, two fold dilutions of DNA of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* were made and their concentrations were measured using Biospectrometer Basic (Eppendorf). Two fold dilutions made up to five times to obtain lowest concentration as possible. Dilutions of *F. necrophorum* were made which carried concentrations from 14 ng/ μ l to 1.13 ng/ μ l and *D. nodosus* DNA concentrations varied from 10.9 ng/ μ l to 0.7 ng/ μ l.

3.6.11 PCR reaction mixture

Total volume was made up to 25 μ l with nuclease free water

<i>Taq</i> buffer A(10X)	-	2.5 μ l
Mgcl ₂	-	1.0 μ l
dNTP mix (10mM)	-	0.3 μ l
16SrRNA (F+R)p mol/ μ l	-	0.6 μ l
<i>lktA</i> (F+R) p mol/ μ l	-	0.6 μ l
<i>Taq</i> DNA polymerase (5U/ μ l)	-	0.3 μ l
Template DNA	-	2.0 μ l
Nuclease-free water	-	17.7 μ l
Total volume	-	<u>25 μl</u>

DNA was serially diluted for determining the lowest concentration that can be detected in the sample and their concentration was estimated using Eppendorf Biospectrometer (Basic).

3.6.12 Amplification

Initial denaturation	94°C-2 min
Step-1	94°C 30 sec
Step-2	60°C 30 sec
Step-3	72°C 30 sec
Initially 5 cycles	
Step-4	94°C 30 sec
Step-5	59°C 30 sec
Step-6	72°C 30 sec
30 cycles for the second reaction	
Final extension	72°C-5 min

3.7 Electrophoresis of PCR Products

3.7.1 Materials

Agarose

TBE Buffer (1X)

Ethidiumbromide (5µg/ml)

100 bp DNA ladder

6X Gel loading dye

3.7.2 Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR product in two percent agarose gel

Amplified products were analysed by agarose gel electrophoresis. Two percent agarose gel was prepared by dissolving required amount of agarose in 1X TBE buffer

and dissolved by heating in a microwave oven and cooled to 50°C and ethidium bromide at the concentration of 0.5 µg per ml was added and mixed. Then, the comb was placed so as to form wells. Then 15 µl of sample DNA was mixed with 3 µl of loading dye (appendix) and was loaded into the wells. Molecular size marker (DNA ladder, Genei, Bangalore) was loaded to the first well. The electrophoresis was carried out at 60 volts for 90 minutes. Sterile distilled water was used as negative control. Polymerase chain reaction amplified products of

D. nodosus targeting 16S rRNA at 783 bp and *F. necrophorum* targeting lktA gene at 500 bp were visualized under U.V trans-illuminator and photographed with Gel Documentation System (Alpha Innotech, AlphaImager HP).

3.8 Purification of PCR product

The amplified products were purified by QIAquick (Gel purification kit 50 Germany) from agarose gel. Purified DNA samples were sent for sequencing to Bioserve India Pvt, Ltd 3-1-135 /1A CNR complex, genome valley main road R.R.Dist, Mallapur, Hyderabad, Telangana- 500076.

3.9 Sequencing

The extracted DNA was amplified by PCR and purified by QIAquick kit and then analysed by agarose gel electrophoresis. The concentration of the extracted DNA was checked by absorption at $\lambda 260$ (Biospectrometer Basic, Eppendorf, Germany) and then sent in 1.5ml microcentrifuge tube on ice pack for sequencing. The DNA samples got sequenced commercially from Bioserve Biotechnologies India Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad, using LktA specific primers.

3.10 Multiple Sequence Analysis of lktA gene

Gel elution was done as per manufacturer's protocol of QIAquick (Gel purification kit 50 Germany). Gel eluted products were submitted for sequencing (Bio serve Biotechnologies India Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad). All the sequences obtained from present isolates were compared with published GenBank sequences by BLAST in NCBI. The lktA gene sequences obtained from Chittoor and Kadapa were submitted to GenBank (Accession no: KP226805; KP226806; MH016737; MH029272; MK169219; MK169219). The selected published lktA sequences from India and different parts of the world with 92-99% homology with present published sequences were trimmed manually and subjected to multiple sequence analysis using BioEdit 7.2.5 software (Hall, 1999). The protein translation of the align sequences was also done using BioEdit 7.2.5 software.

3.11 Phylogenetic analysis

All the multiple aligned lktA sequences were subjected to phylogenetic analysis by Neighbour Joining method using Mega 7 software (Kumar *et al.*, 2016).

3.12 Statistical analysis

Chi square test was employed for data analysis using computer software a interactive calculation tool for chi-square tests of goodness of fit and independence (Preacher, 2001).

CHAPTER-IV

RESULTS

4.1 Collection of samples from field

A total of 172 footswabs suspected for footrot affected sheep and goat subjected to DNA extraction by boiling the sample at 95°C for 5min. (Fig. 1) were collected and 85 gingival swabs (Fig. 2) from both healthy and diseased flocks were collected

Fig 1. Collection of Footswabs

Fig 2. Collection of Gingival Swabs

4.2 Gross examination of disease

Gross examination of affected sheep flock revealed a foul and rotting smell of feet. On clear examination of hooves, erosion of interdigital skin, and sloughing of hooves could be noticed in some sheep. Clinical examination of footrot affected sheep revealed limping with affected limbs raised.

Footrot affected animals showed lesions as presented in Fig-3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10.

Fig 3: Necrosis of inner hoof

Fig 4: Interdigital dermatitis

Fig 5: Interdigital dermatitis

Fig 6: Severe hoof erosion

Fig. 7. Interdigital dermatitis Score 1

Fig.8. Interdigital dermatitis Score 2

Fig.9. Interdigital dermatitis Score 3

Fig.10. Interdigital dermatitis Score 4

4.3 Standardisation of Duplex PCR

The least amount of primer dilution for detecting the sensitivity of duplex PCR was 2.5 pmol for successfully amplifying the target DNA in the sample.

The sensitivity of duplex PCR in detecting *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* is found to be up to the DNA concentrations of 2^{-2} to 2^{-5} and primer concentration from 25 pmol to 2.5 pmol respectively Fig-7 concentration of 1.13 ng/ μ l and 0.7 ng/ μ l of *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* at a dilution of 2^{-5} and the detection of various DNA concentrations is shown in the Fig.7 and gel picture showing different concentrations is shown in Fig.13,14.

Table no.4 *F. necrophorum* DNA dilutions

Dilution	2	4	8	16	32
DNA Concentration	14 ng/ μ l	4.5 ng/ μ l	1.38 ng/ μ l	1.3 ng/ μ l	1.13 ng/ μ l
Absorbance($A^{280/260}$)	1.51	1.50	1.45	1.22	0.94

Table no.5 *D. nodosus* DNA dilutions

Dilution	2	4	8	16	32
DNA Concentration	10.9 ng/ μ l	8.8 ng/ μ l	3.4 ng/ μ l	2.7 ng/ μ l	0.7 ng/ μ l
Absorbance($A^{280/260}$)	16.08	4.65	3.03	2.38	1.93

The duplex PCR sensitivity was standardised in detecting the DNA concentration of 1.13 ng/ μ l of *F. necrophorum* DNA and 0.7 ng/ μ l of *D. nodosus* DNA with a primer concentration of 2.5 pmol.

Fig 11. Duplex PCR sensitivity in detecting different conc of DNA

Fig 12. Agarose gel showing the PCR amplification of 16S rRNA gene

L : **Ladder (100 bp)**
M1 : **Negative Control**
M2, M3 : **Field Samples Positive for 16S rRNA Gene**

Fig 13. Agarose gel showing the PCR amplification of LktA gene

- L** : Ladder (100 bp)
M1 : Positive Control
M2 : Negative Control
M3 and M4 : Field samples Positive for lktA gene

Fig 14. Duplex PCR with different conc. of primers

L : **Ladder (100 bp)**
M : **Negative Control**
M1, M2, M3, M4 : **Oligonucleotide Primer Dilutions**

Fig 15. Duplex PCR with different conc. of DNA

- L** : **Ladder (100 bp)**
M1 : **Negative Control**
M2, M3, M4, M5 : **DNA Dilutions (4, 8, 16, 32)**

Fig 16. Duplex PCR with field sample

L : **Ladder (100 bp)**
M : **Negative Control**
M2, M3 : **Positive Field Samples**

4.4 Screening of samples for the detection of *lktA* gene and 16S rRNA by duplex PCR

The results of duplex PCR targeting 16S rRNA of *D. nodosus* and *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum* was presented in the Table No. (6). Out of total 172 samples tested 43(25.0%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, 18 (10.46%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 34 (19.8%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. Out of 103 sheep samples tested 30 (29.1%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, only 3 (2.9%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 16 (15.5%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. Out of 69 goat samples tested 13 (18.8%) were positive for *D. nodosus* and 15 (21.7%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 18 (26.0%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*.

Table no 6. Samples positive for footrot

Species	No. Of Samples screened by Dulex PCR	<i>D. nodosus</i> positives (%)	<i>F. necrophorum</i> positives (%)	<i>D. nodosus</i> and <i>F. necrophorum</i> positives (%)
Sheep	103	30 (29.1%)	3 (2.9%)	16 (15.5%)
Goat	69	13 (18.8%)	15 (21.7%)	18 (26%)
Total	172	43 (25.0%)	18 (10.46%)	34 (19.8%)

Fig.17. Comparison of *D.nodosus* positives in sheep and goat

Fig.18. Comparison of *F. necrophorum* positives in sheep and goat

Fig.19. Combined presence of *D.nodosus* and *F.necrophorum* in Sheep and Goats

Fig.20. Total *F.necrophorum*, and *D.nodosus*

4.5 Causal association of *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* in footrot of sheep and goat.

To determine association between these two anaerobic organisms in causing footrot in sheep and goat, a statistical analysis was carried out using Chi square (χ^2) test.

Table no.7 Details of statistical analysis

	<i>D. nodosus</i> Positives	<i>D. nodosus</i> negatives	Total
<i>F. necrophorum</i> positives	34	18	67
<i>F. necrophorum</i> negatives	43	77	105
Total	77	95	172

The association between *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in footrot samples was found to be statistically significant.

4.6 Characterisation of lktA gene

4.6.1. Multiple sequence analysis

The characterisation of lktA gene was done by multiple sequence analysis of partial *lktA* sequences retrieved from the Genbank NCBI with 94-99% homology and were analysed using the ClustalW of MEGA4 (Fig.18,19). The corresponding translated protein sequences were also aligned using same software and shown in the (Fig.20). All the amplified partial lktA gene sequences of the *F. necrophorum* isolates were found to be identical with 99% homology.

The multiple sequence analysis of the published partial lktA gene of the isolate (KP226806; KP226805) from this region with selected published sequences of lktA from GenBank revealed 99% homology with sequence (JX678873; FJ230831; KY130428) obtained from *F. necrophorm* isolate from Australia, New Zealand and China.

Fig 21. Multiple sequence alignment of partial *lktA* gene sequences of *F. necrophorum*

Fig 23. Aminoacid sequences of the multiple alignment with substitutions at various locations. (*) end, (?)missing information sites, (-) alignment gaps

The sequence homology with remaining sequences of *lktA* was found to be ranging from 96-92%. The published *lktA* sequence from *F. necrophorum* of sheep of Andhra Pradesh KP226806 and KP226806 showed high similarity with five single nucleotide substitution at T131C, C151T, C205T, G217A, C288T and A308G. The sequences from Australia, New Zealand and China were almost identical to KP226806 with only two substitutions at T131C and C205T. The sequences from india_UP (KJ404071) and India_Kashmir (JF911484) were identical with 100% homology. The sequences from Australia (JX678871), India_Jammu (JX104210), China (JQ323096) and New Zealand (HQ380205) were almost identical and showing variation from the local sequences with substitutions at different positions ranging from 34 to 316 and three gap at position 69-71.

The major nucleotide substitutions along with the reflected amino acid substitution are presented in the table No.8. Majority of single nucleotide substitution was reflected into amino acid substitutions with few exceptions at positions T79C, G81A, T165C, T166A, T245G, A251G, C288T did not reflected changes in corresponding amino acid sequences.

4.6.2. Phylogenetic Analysis of *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum*

The neighbour joining tree was constructed using software MEGA4 as shown in Fig. 17. The phylogenetic analysis of the *lktA* gene partial sequences of present study (KP226805; KP22806) with the selected published sequences of *lktA* revealed close segregation of KP226805 as distinct root with sequences from Australia (JX678873), China (KY130428) and New Zealand (FJ230831). The *lktA* sequence KP226806 from sheep of India found to be highly conserved and positioned as root for the taxas (KP226805; JX648295; JX678873; KY130428; FJ230831) from Newzeland, China, Australia and India_AP in the cluster. The other cluster sequences from India_UP (KJ404071) and India_kashmir (JF911484) with 100% homology clustered in to distinct clade but with moderate bootstrap value (55%). The other Indian sequence from Jammu (JX104210) formed close cluster with the Australian sequence (JX678871) with highest bootstrap value (99%).

Fig 24. Evolutionary relationships of 12 taxa

The evolutionary history was inferred using the Neighbor Joining method. The bootstrap consensus tree inferred from 1000 replicates is taken to represent the evolutionary history of the taxa analyzed. Branches corresponding to partitions reproduced in less than 50% bootstrap replicates are collapsed. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown next to the branches. Phylogenetic analyses were conducted in MEGA4.

Table no.8 Nucleotide and corresponding amino acid substitutions of lktA Gene aligned sequences.

S.no	Nucleotide Substitutions	Amino acid Substitution	Sequences exhibiting substituions
1	G5C	R2T	KY130428
2	T30C	K11E	JX648295
3	A32G	K11R	JX104210
4	G34A	A11K	JX678871;JX104210 JQ2323096;HQ380205
5	T43C	*15Q	JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096;HQ380205
6	C49A	Q17K	JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096;HQ380205
7	C55T	R19W	JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096;HQ380205
8	A63C	K21N	JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096;HQ380205
9	T79C	-	HQ380205
10	G81A	-	JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096
11	T85C	W27R	HQ380205
12	C88T	F29L	HQ380205
13	G89T	R30W	HQ380205
14	G103A	D35N	KJ404071;JF911484 JX678871;JX104210 JQ323096
15	T131C	F44S	KP226805
16	T133C	F45L	KJ404071;JF911484 JQ323096;HQ380205
17	T145C	W49R	KJ404071;JF911484 JQ323096;HQ380205
18	C151T	R51C	KP226805;JX678873 FJ230831;KY130428 JX648295;JX678871 JX104210
19	C151A	R51S	HQ380205
20	T160C	W54R	KJ404071;JX648295 JF911484;JQ323096 HQ380205
21	A163G	S55G	KJ404071;JF911484 JQ323096
22	T165C	-	JX678871;JX104210 HQ380205
23	T166A	-	KJ404071;JF911484 JQ323096
24	T172C	W58R	KJ404071;JF911484 JX678871; JX104210

			JQ323096; HQ380205
25	C192G	F64L	JX648295
26	T193C	C65R	KJ404071; JF911484 JQ323096
27	T195G	C65W	JX648295
28	C205T	R69C	KP226805; KJ404071 JF911484; JF678871 JX104210; JQ323096 HQ380205
29	G214A	D72N	JX678871; JX104210 HQ380205
30	G217A	G73R	KP226805; JX678873 FJ230831; KY130428 JX678871; JX104210 HQ380205
31	T222G	S74R	JX648295
32	T245G	-	JX648295
33	T246G	F82W	JX648295
34	A247G	S83G	KJ404071; JF911484 JF678871; JX104210 JQ323096; HQ380205
35	A250G	K84G	JX648295
36	A251G	-	JX648295
37	C258A	S86R	JX648295
38	C288T	-	KP226805; JX678873 FJ230831; KY130428 KJ404071; JX648295 JF911484
39	C289T	R97C	JF911484; JX678871 JX104210; JQ323096 HQ380205
40	G293A	S98N	KJ404071; JF911484 JX678871; JX104210 JQ323096; HQ380205
41	T304C	C102R	KJ404071; JF911484 JQ323096
42	A308G	N103S	KP226805; JX678873 FJ230831; KY130428 KJ404071; JF911484 JX678871; JX104210 JQ323096; HQ380205
43	T309A	N103R	JX648295
44	T310A	W104R	JX648295
45	T310C	W104R	JF911484; JX678871 JX104210; JQ323096 HQ380205
46	T316G	C106G	KJ404071; JF911484 JX104210; JQ323096 HQ380205

4.7 Comparison of Full genome of *lktA* with amplified partial sequences using BRIG

Fig 25. *lktA* full genome (AF312861) circular presentation with partial sequences

The *F. necrophorum* lktA full Genome AF312861 has been retrieved from the Genbank along with partial lktA sequences of India, Australia and New Zealand to compare their positions of similarity on genome using the BRIG Ring image generator V 0.95 software (Alikhan, 2011) which is a simple prokaryote genome comparison tool. The full lktA full Genome AF312861 consists of oppf (1-211bp), lktB (685-2337bp), lktA (2353-12078bp), lktC (12075-12512) where the partial lktA sequences represent their location range from which helps in identifying the BLAST matches to the full genomes to understand unassembled sequence data, the comparison of partial lktA sequences of *F. necrophorum* used in identifying the reference region in lktA full genome which is located in 8100-9200bp.

CHAPTER-V

DISCUSSION

Footrot is a contagious hoof disease of sheep and goats begins as an interdigital dermatitis, causing lesions on the inter digital wall of the hoof. This causes separation of the hard horn from the foot where disease can be seen spreading into deep layers of hoof. It causes economic loss to the farmers in terms of, loss of wool strength, and reduced body weight resulting in poor quality of meat (Marshall *et al*, 1991; Bennett *et al.*, 2011).

The occurrence of footrot is seen in different seasons in temperate regions (Egerton and Thorley, 1981; Glynn, 1993 and Ghimire *et al*, 1996). Rainy season was seen to be more favourable for footrot with conditions such as moderate temperature, moist soils and more relative humidity. The disease spreads between sheep via pasture or pen floor when the environmental conditions were conducive (Whittington and Nicholas 1995; Green and George, 2008). Muzafar *et al.* (2015) showed that direct transmission can occur rapidly. Transmission of footrot is influenced by environmental conditions such as moisture, temperature, and pasture (Graham and Egerton, 1968, Depiazzi *et al.*, 1998;). Wet and relatively warm weather (mean temperature above 10°C) facilitates transmission, whereas hot, dry weather inhibits its spread (Graham and Egerton, 1968; Depiazzi *et al.*, 1998). The severity of footrot depends on the virulence of causative organisms (Stewart *et al.*, 1986), along with environmental conditions (Graham and Egerton, 1968; Depiazzi *et al.*, 1998), management practices in farms (Wassink *et al.*, 2003), susceptibility of the host (Emery *et al.*, 1984), and secondary bacteria that proliferate the lesion (Witcomb *et al.*, 2014; Egerton *et al.*, 1969). In addition, some sort of initial damage to the inter

digital skin is believed to be required for the disease to develop (Beveridge, 1941 Egerton *et al.*, 1969). Only a short exposure time of susceptible sheep to contaminated grounds was enough for indirect transmission to occur in the field (Whittington, 1995). In India the initial reports of footrot were from the temperate climates of Jamm and Kashmir (Wani *et al.* 2004; Hussain *et al.* 2009; Farooq *et al.* 2010; Rather *et al.* 2011). Paradoxically the disease was also found to be prevalent in the temperate climates of southern India like Andhra Pradesh showing prevalence even in peak summer months (Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013; Vinod *et al.*,2013). The disease became endemic in the states of Jammu and Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Kerala and Andhra Pradesh with seasonal outbreaks (Wani *et al.*, 2007; Farooq *et al.*, 2010; Thomas *et al.* 2011, Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013; Vinod *et al.*, 2013; Vinod *et al.*, 2015; Vinod *et al.*, 2016).

Though *D. nodosus* was proved as causative agent for footrot as per Koch's molecular postulates (Kennan *et al.*, 2001; 2010), *F. necrophorum* was also frequently found to be associated with it along with other etiological agents like *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Treponema* (Bennett *et al.*, 2009; Zhou *et al.*, 2009; Egerton *et al.*, 1969). The debate over years whether the causative agent is *D. nodosus* or *F. necrophorum* in causing disease was under constant rebound in arriving at conclusions, so the research insight into causative agent pointed out at *D. nodosus*, is involved in causing infection in early stages (Witcomb *et al.*, 2014). Later, the presence of *F. necrophorum* in the footrot lesions in association with *D. nodosus* proved to support hypothesis of its involvement in the pathogenesis of the disease. *Fusobacterium necrophorum* is involved in increasing the severity of the lesion, and considered as an opportunistic secondary pathogen (Witcomb *et al.*, 2014; Witcomb *et al.*, 2015). So considering its role, the detection of *F. necrophorum* along with *D.*

nodosus from footrot lesions carries a major importance in knowing the onset and pathogenesis of footrot. Both the organisms are Gram negative, fastidious, slow growing strict anaerobes, isolation of these organisms is very tedious and time consuming. Thus, specific and sensitive molecular methods are necessary for the easy and confirmative detection of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. The application of PCR for amplification of specific DNA sequences have shown considerable promise for the development of highly sensitive and specific diagnostic tests in several areas since the late 1980s. The PCR has been highlighted as a rapid and accurate method for detection of low copy number of genes. The sensitivity and specificity of the PCR were confirmed by amplification of specific target DNA under unique conditions. So, rapid identification of these organisms by PCR is a proven reliable alternative (Gradin and Schmitz, 1977; Langworth, 1977; Moor *et al.* 2005). The application of PCR assay in detection and identification has made isolation procedures unnecessary which reduces laboratory time from three to four weeks to one day (Wani and Samantha, 2006). Hence, in the present investigation PCR assay is chosen for detection of *D. nodosus* from foot lesions targeting 16S rRNA.

The oligonucleotide primers targeting 16S rRNA was used as per the method described earlier (La Fontaine *et al.*, 1993) and the PCR protocol standardised in this laboratory (Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013). The *lktA* protein of *F. necrophorum* was considered to be a major virulence factor in the course of footrot disease due to the killing effect on neutrophilic leukocyte of ruminant (Tan *et al.*, 1996; Narayanan *et al.*, 2001). The leukotoxin gene has three components *lktB*, *lktA*, and *lktC* in its operon where *lktA* is highly conserved and the subject of interest in detecting its role in footrot and differentiating it from the other causative agents from the complex microbial load of foot. Due to the difficulty of isolation of *F. necrophorum* from

lesion which is strict anaerobic nature and more sensitive to oxygen, the molecular techniques are found to be more sensitive than culture (Moore *et al.*, 2005). Various researchers targeted 16S rRNA gene in *D. nodosus* and *lktA* gene in *F. necrophorum* from footrot lesions for PCR based diagnosis in India (Wani *et al.*, 2004), (Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013), (Nayakwadi *et al.*, 2014; Anto *et al.*, 2014; Vinod *et al.*, 2016). The PCR targeting *LktA* gene coding for leukotoxin synthesis is used as per the method described earlier (Zhou *et al.*, 2009) and the PCR protocol standardized in this laboratory (Vinod *et al.*, 2016).

Despite the advantages offered by the initial PCR assay for separate amplification of target genes of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* over the traditional isolation methods, it requires two separate reactions for amplification of target genes from footrot lesions. To make the test simple and for simultaneous amplification of the target genes, the duplex PCR was standardised in the present study.

Duplex PCR for direct detection of 16S rRNA of *D. nodosus* and *lktA* of *F. necrophorum* was standardized using the *D. nodosus* (serogroup I) cultures maintained in the laboratory and *F. necrophorum* positive DNA sample obtained from UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK, London, United Kingdom. In the present study, DNA was extracted from the cultures of *D. nodosus* using a rapid boiling method as described by Cox (1992), Wani *et al.*, (2007) and Sreenivasulu *et al.*, (2013). This method was selected because of its simplicity and its applicability to study field samples.

To evaluate the sensitivity of the duplex PCR, serial dilutions of template DNA and primers was made for detecting the lowest possible concentration of sample DNA and minimum concentrations of primers in an effective way to build a

lucid protocol to detect the presence of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in footrot sample. The primer pairs at the concentration of 2.5 pmol each were found optimal for successfully amplifying the target DNA in the sample, in duplex PCR. The sensitivity of duplex PCR in detecting *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* was tested with serial dilutions of the template(positive control DNA) from 14 ng/μl to 1.13 ng/μl. The duplex PCR was able to optimally amplify the targets at template concentrations as low as 1.13 ng/μl and 2.7 ng/μl for *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* respectively.

In the present study, total of 81 flocks of sheep and goat from Nellore, Chittoor, Kadapa, East Godavari, and Anathapur districts of Andhra Pradesh were inspected for footrot cases during the period i.e January to November, 2018. The data were recorded based on the clinical symptoms of footrot as per the previous reports (Sreenivasulu *et al.*, 2013; Vinod *et al.*, 2013). Presence of necrotic epidermal tissue and foul smelling discharges, loss of hoof layers exposing infected tissue from the lesions characteristic of footrot in severe cases were observed. The clinical signs and the lesions observed were similar to the reports of Wani and Samanta. (2006); Sreenivasulu *et al.* (2013), Vinod *et al.* (2015), Vinod *et al.* (2016).

Out of total 172 samples tested, 43(25.0%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, 18(10.46%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 34 (19.8%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. The overall prevalence of *F. necrophorum* in sheep and goat affected with footrot during the period of study was 30.2 %, whereas shaheen (2013) reported 26% prevalence of *F. necrophorum* alone from footrot samples of sheep from temperate regions of Jammu and Kashmir. Out of 103 sheep samples tested, 30 (29.1%) were positive for *D.nodosus* alone, only 3 (2.9%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 16 (15.5%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. This denotes the overall prevalence of 18.4% of *F. necrophorum* from

sheep footrot samples. Vinod *et al.*, (2016) reported 22.9% prevalence of *F. necrophorum* along with *D. nodosus* (66.0%) from samples of footrot in sheep in Andhra Pradesh. The high prevalence of *D. nodosus* (30.2%) when compared with *F. necrophorum* (27.5%) in the present study is in agreement with the previous reports of Vinod *et al.* (2016) who reported 66% prevalence of *D. nodosus*. Farooq *et al.* (2015; 2018) reported 30% prevalence of *D. nodosus* and 26% prevalence of *F. necrophorum* with a range of 20-34.8% from footrot case in Jammu and Kashmir region. Whereas Bennett *et al.* (2009) reported 45% prevalence of both *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* from footrot cases of sheep in New Zealand. The low prevalence of *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in the swabs collected from typical footrot cases might be attributed to various factors like, time of collection, method of DNA extraction and more precisely the PCR assay might be inhibited by other compounds extracted from the swab. The sampling procedure employed might not come in contact with the organisms present in deeper parts of tissue Bennett *et al.* (2009). In contrast, Zhou *et al.* (2009) reported 13 positives out of the 14 samples tested from sheep footrot.

Samples were also collected from footrot cases in goats in the present study. Out of 69 goat samples tested, 13 (18.8%) were positive for *D. nodosus* and 15 (21.7%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 18 (26%) were positive for both the organisms which denotes an overall prevalence of 47.8% of *F. necrophorum*. The high prevalence of *F. necrophorum* from goat samples was also reported by Vinod *et al.* (2016) who reported an overall prevalence of *F. necrophorum* in 84.8% of the samples. Zhou *et al.* (2009) reported *lktA* gene of *F. necrophorum* in five out of six samples tested. The reason for high prevalence of *F. necrophorum* from goat samples might be attributed to smaller sample size, geographical or species predisposition

when compared to sheep. Since the available literature is very scanty on prevalence studies of *F. necrophorum* in goats, further investigations are required to understand the epidemiology of footrot in this species.

In the present investigation, the causal association between *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* was evaluated by statistical analysis. These two anaerobes are significantly associated with each other in footrot lesions. However, in the present study, less than 50% of the positive samples (34 out of 77) showed *F. necrophorum* and 34 out of 67 revealed *D. nodosus*. Both bacteria were detected in 19.7% of the total samples screened. These results are in agreement with the findings of Farooq *et al.* (2015) who reported statistically significant association of 11.5% of total positive samples harbouring both *D.nodosus* and *F.necrophorum*. Based on the present results in support of previous findings, it is not possible to conclude with certainty that both bacteria are together required for disease manifestation based on the statistical association. *Fusobacterium necrophorum* is believed to create anaerobic micro-environment in the infected hoofs by inducing necrosis which helps *D. nodosus* to establish itself and cause footrot (Farooq *et al.*, 2015). In contrary, Bennett *et al.* (2009) reported that initiation of footrot is done by *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* is involved in increasing the severity of lesions and a high degree of association of these two organisms under field conditions. Witcomb *et al*, (2014; 2015) reported that *F. necrophorum* is involved in increasing the severity of the lesion, and considered as an opportunistic secondary pathogen.

The available literature also suggest that *F. necrophorum* is thought to be excreted in the faeces colonising in the foot of sheep and goat and causing infection during favourable conditions (Clark *et al.*,1985). The excreted organism might contaminate the feed, and water thereby inhabiting the gingival sulcus. In sheep, *F.*

necrophorum has been isolated from gingival swabs and healthy and footrot affected feet with unknown significance of these sites as reservoirs (Bennett *et al.* 2009). Hence, attempts were made in the present investigation to demonstrate *F. necrophorum* genome from gingival swabs. Though, the organisms has been widely assumed to be ubiquitous in sheep faeces and soil, attempts made in the present investigation to identity the *F. necrophorum* genome from gingival swabs did not reveal any results which makes the assumption unsubstantiated (Winter, 2004).

The characterisation of *lktA* gene is done by the multiple sequence analysis of partial *lktA* sequences retrieved from the Genbank NCBI with 94-99% homology and were analysed using the ClustalW of MEGA4. The corresponding translated protein sequences were also aligned using the same software. All the amplified partial *lktA* gene sequences of the *F. necrophorum* isolates were found to be identical with 99% homology. The multiple sequence analysis of the published partial *lktA* gene (KP226806; KP226805) from this region with selected published sequences of *lktA* from GenBank revealed 99% homology with sequence (JX678873; FJ230831; KY130428) obtained from *F. necrophorm* isolate from Australia, New Zealand and China.

The sequence homology with remaining sequences of *lktA* was found to be ranging from 96-92%. The published *lktA* sequence from *F. necrophorum* of sheep of Andhra Pradesh (KP226806 and KP226806) showed high similarity with five single nucleotide substitution at T131C, C151T, C205T, G217A, C288T and A308G. The sequences from Australia, New Zealand and China were almost identical to KP226806 with only two substitutions at T131C and C205T. The sequences from india_UP (KJ404071) and India_Kashmir (JF911484) were identical with 100% homology. The sequences from Australia (JX678871), India_Jammu (JX104210),

China (JQ323096) and New Zealand (HQ380205) were almost identical and showed variation from the local sequences with substitutions at different positions ranging from 34 to 316 and three gap at position 69-71.

Majority of single nucleotide substitution were reflected into amino acid substitutions with few exceptions at positions T79C, G81A, T165C, T166A, T245G, A251G and C288T which did not reflect changes in corresponding amino acid sequences.

To derive the phylogenetic relationship of various *lktA* partial sequences (Zhou and Hickford., 2008; Farooq *et al.*, 2018) the neighbour joining tree was constructed using software MEGA4. The phylogenetic analysis of the *lktA* gene partial sequences of present study (KP226805; KP22806) with the selected published sequences of *lktA* revealed close segregation of KP226805 as distinct root with sequences from Australia (JX678873), China (KY130428) and New Zealand (FJ230831). The *lktA* sequence KP226806 from sheep of India was found to be highly conserved and positioned as root for the taxas (KP226805; JX648295; JX678873; KY130428; FJ230831) from New Zealand, China, Australia and India_AP in the cluster. The other cluster sequences from India_UP (KJ404071) and India_kashmir (JF911484) clustered in to distinct clade with 100% homology but with moderate bootstrap value (55%).

The other Indian sequence from Jammu (JX104210) formed close cluster with the Australian sequence (JX678871) with highest bootstrap value (99%). Dorsch *et al.* (2001) reclassified the *F. necrophorum* strain as *F. equinum* based on the phylogenetic analysis of 16s rRNA gene and DND-DNA hybridisation. Similarly, Zhou *et al.* (2009) reported the existence of four variants of *F. necrophorum* with high

species specificity in cattle, sheep and goat based on PCR- single standard conformational polymorphism and phylogenetic analysis. Farooq *et al.* (2018) reported presence of four variants of *F. necrophorum* based on PCR- single standard conformational polymorphism and phylogenetic analysis from the sheep footrot lesions. The phylogenetic analysis of present investigation did not reveal any clue to arrive at such conclusions. The investigation is very preliminary to demonstrate the mere presence of *F. necrophorum* as causative of footrot in the region with simple molecular test. Further detailed investigation is needed to arrive at a decisive conclusion regarding the existence of strain variations of *F. necrophorum* in footrot of sheep and goat in the region.

CHAPTER-VI

SUMMARY

Footrot is a contagious bacterial disease of sheep and goat supposed to be caused by *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. The study was undertaken to determine the causal association between *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum* in footrot, duplex PCR was standardized for simultaneous detection of these causative agents and characterisation of *lktA* gene,

For duplex PCR, DNA was extracted from footrot lesions of sheep and goat by boiling method. Standardisation was done adopting serial dilutions of positive template DNA and oligonucleotide primers targeting 16S rRNA of *D. nodosus*. *LktA* gene primers were designed and used in standardization of duplex PCR for *F. necrophorum* due to its highly conserved property and unique nature.

The optimum concentration of primers was found to be 2.5 pmol/ μ l and the sensitivity was 0.7 ng/ μ l for duplex PCR assay. This makes the test simple for simultaneous amplification of the target genes in detecting the causative agents.

The samples were screened from reported outbreaks in Chittoor, Nellore, Kadapa, Ananthapur and East Godavari districts of Andhra Pradesh by the duplex PCR. A total of 81 flocks were screened and 172 samples were tested. Forty three (25.0%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, 18 (10.46%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 34 (19.8%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. Out of 103 sheep samples tested, 30 (29.1%) were positive for *D. nodosus*, only 3 (2.9%) were positive for *F. necrophorum* and 16 (15.5%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*. Out of 69 goat samples tested, 13 (18.8%) were positive for *D.*

nodosus 15 (21.7%) for *F. necrophorum* and 18 (26.0%) were positive for both *D. nodosus* and *F. necrophorum*.

In the present investigation, the causal association between *F. necrophorum* and *D. nodosus* by statistical analysis revealed that two anaerobes are significantly associated with each other in footrot lesions. However, in the present study less than 50% of positive samples (34 out of 77 show *F. necrophorum* and 34 out of 67 revealed *D. nodosus*) contain both the bacteria which accounts for 19.7% of the total samples screened.

The characterisation of *lktA* gene was done by multiple sequence analysis of partial *lktA* sequences retrieved from the Genbank NCBI with 94-99% homology. The multiple sequence analysis of the published partial *lktA* gene of the isolate (KP226806; KP226805) from this region with selected published sequences of *lktA* from GenBank revealed 99% homology with sequence (JX678873; FJ230831; KY130428) obtained from *F. necrophorm* isolate from Australia, New Zealand and China.

The sequences from Australia (JX678871), India_Jammu (JX104210), China (JQ323096) and New Zealand (HQ380205) were almost identical and showed variation from the local sequences with substitutions at different positions ranging from 34 to 316 and three gap at position 69-71. Majority of single nucleotide substitution reflected into amino acid substitutions with few exceptions.

The phylogenetic analysis of the *lktA* gene partial sequences the present study (KP226805; KP22806) with the selected published sequences of *lktA* revealed close segregation of KP226805 as distinct root with sequences from Australia(JX678873), China (KY130428) and New Zealand (FJ230831). The *lktA*

sequence KP226806 from sheep of India was found to be highly conserved and positioned as root for the taxas (KP226805; JX648295; JX678873; KY130428; FJ230831) from New Zealand, China, Australia and India_AP in the cluster. The other cluster sequences from India_UP(KJ404071) and India kashmir (JF911484) with 100% homology exhibited the cluster in to distinct clade but with moderate bootstrap value (55%).

The study is a preliminary investigation to demonstrate causal association of *F. necrophorum* with *D. nodosus* in causing footrot in the region with a simple molecular test.

The significance after statistical association alone cannot confirm the association of

F. necrophorum in causing footrot in sheep. The statistical data from present and previous reports demonstrated close association between the organisms in goats when compared to sheep, which needs further thorough epidemiological investigation to confirm the hypothesis.

LITERATURE CITED

- Abbott K A, and Lewis C J 2005 Current approaches to the management of ovine footrot. *The Veterinary Journal* 169, 28-41.
- Abe P M, Kendall C J, Stauffer L R and Holland J W 1979 Hemolytic activity of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* culture supernatants due to presence of phospholipase A and lysophospholipase. *American Journal of Veterinary Research*, 40, 92-96.
- Acharya, R M 1982 Sheep and Goat Breeds of India. Food and Agricultural Organization, United Nations, Rome, Italy.
- Alessandro Foddai, Laura E Green, Sam A Mason and Jasmeet Kaler 2012 Evaluating observer agreement of scoring systems for foot integrity and footrot lesions in sheep *BMC Veterinary Research* 2012, 8:65.
- Alibasoglu M and Yesildere T 1988 Veteriner Sistemik Patoloji. 2nd edn. Ankara: Konia, 118-119p.
- Alikhan NF , Petty NK, Ben Zakour NL, and Beatson SA 2011 BLAST Ring Image Generator (BRIG): simple prokaryote genome comparisons, *BMC Genomics*, 12:402.
- Amess J A, O'Neill W, Ni Giollariabhaigh C, Dytrych J K 2007 A six-month audit of the isolation of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from patients with sore throat in a district general hospital. *Br. J. Biomed. Sci* ,16-32.
- Amoako K K, Goto Y, Shinjo T 1994 Studies on the factors affecting the hemolytic activity of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *J. Vet. Microbiol.* 41, 11–8.
- Amoako, K K, Goto, Y, Shinjo, T 1993 Comparison of extracellular enzymes of *Fusobacterium necrophorum subsp. necrophorum* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum subsp. funduliforme*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 31, 2244–2247.
- Antiabong J F, Boardman W, Smith I, Brown M H, Ball A S, and Goodman A E 2013 “Cycliplex PCR” confirmation of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* isolates from

captive wallabies: a rapid and accurate approach. *Anaerobe* 19, 44–49.

- Anto.L, Joseph.S, Mini.M, and Pellissery.A.J 2014 Identification of anaerobic and concomitant aerobic bacterial etiologies in caprine footrot *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci* (2014) 3(4): 197-206.
- Anton AI, Martinez-Murcia, A J and Rodriguez-Valera, F 1998 Sequence diversity in the 16S-23S intergenic spacer region (ISR) of the rRNA operons in representatives of the *Escherichia coli* ECOR collection. *J Mol Evol* 47, 62–72.
- Baron EJ, Citron DM 1997 Anaerobic identification flowchart using minimal laboratory resources. *Clin Infect Dis* 25(Suppl. 2):S143–S146.
- Belloy L Giacometti M, Boujon P, Waldvogel, A 2007 Detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* in wild ungulates (*capra ibex ibex and ovis aries musimon*) and domestic sheep suffering from foot rot using a two-step polymerase chain reaction. *Journal of Wildlife Diseases* 43, 82-88.
- Bennett G, Trotter C, Zhou H, van Loenen A, Gibbs J, and Hickford J G, 2011. *Fusobacterium necrophorum* in New Zealand, the strains present on the hooves of lame dairy cattle and sheep and goats with footrot. *N.Z. Vet. J.*
- Bennett G, van Loenen A, Zhou H, Sedcole R, Hickford J 2009 The detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from footrot lesions in New Zealand goats. *Anaerobe* 15, 177.
- Bennett G, Zhou H, Hickford J G 2010 Undetected lktA genes within *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *J. Med. Microbiol.* 59, 499-500.
- Bennett, G.N 1994 Lincoln University Digital Thesis *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* in ruminants with lameness and footrot.
- Berg J N and Scanlan CM 1982 Studies of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from bovine hepatic abscesses:biotypes. quantitation, virulence, and antibiotic susceptibility. *American Journal of Veterinary Research*,43,1580-1586.
- Beveridge W I B 1938 Footrot in sheep: a preliminary note on the probable causal agent. *Journal of the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research* 11: 1-3.

- Beveridge W I B 1941 Footrot in sheep a transmissible disease due to infection with *Fusiformis nodosus*. Studies on its cause, epidemiology and control. Council for Scientific and Industrial Research.
- Beveridge W I B 1983 Bacterial diseases of cattle, sheep and goats. Published by Australian Government Publishing Service, pp. 108-18.
- Billington S J, Johnston J.L, Rood J I 1996 Virulence regions and virulence factors of the ovine footrot pathogen, *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* (96)00379-5.
- Bishop S C and Morris C A 2007 Genetics of disease resistance in sheep and goats. *Small Rumin. Res.* 70, 48-59.
- Brook I 2002 Microbiology of polymicrobial abscesses and implications for therapy. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 50(6):805–10.
- Brook I and Frazier EH 1997 The aerobic and anaerobic bacteriology of perirectal abscesses. *J Clin Microbiol* 35: 2974-2976.
- Brook I, and Walker J 1986 Isolation of capsulate anaerobic bacteria from orofacial abscesses. *J Med Microbiol* 22(2):171–4.
- Brook I. Fusobacterial infections in children. *J Infect* 1994;28:155–65.
- Buller NB, Eamens G. Ovine Footrot 2014 Australian and New Zealand Standard Diagnostic Procedure. Australian Government.
- Buquicchio F and Spruyt M 2018 Gene runner software version 6.5.51 Beta.
- C.F. Scholz, H. Bruggemann, H.B. Lomholt, H. Tettelin, M. Kilian 2016 Genome stability of *Propionibacterium acnes*: a comprehensive study of indels and homopolymeric tracts, *Sci. Rep.* 6 20662.
- Cagatay IF, and Hickford JGH 2006 Characterization of footrot bacteria *Dichelobacter nodosus* using PCR amplification and DNA sequence analysis. *Turk J Vet Anim Sci* 30: 53-59
- Cagatay T I, Hickford J G 2008 Glycosylation of type-IV fimbriae of *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Vet Microbiol.* 126, 160-7.

- Calvo-Bado LA, Oakley B B, Dowd S E, Green L E, Medley G F, Ul-Hassan, A Bateman, V Gaze, W Witcomb, L Grogono-Thomas, R Kaler, J Russell, C L and Wellington, E.M 2011 Ovine pedometrics: the first study of the ovine foot 16S rRNA-based microbiome. *The ISME Journal*.
- Cederlöf S E, Hansen T, Klaas I C and Angen O 2013 An evaluation of the ability of *Dichelobacter nodosus* to survive in soil. *Acta Veterinaria Scandinavica*. 55, p.4.
- Chabert P, Flandrin P and Huzard J B 1791 Instructions et observations sur les maladies des animaux domestiques. Veuve Vallat La Chapeille, Paris, France.
- Chetwin, D H, Whitehead L C, and Thorley S E 1991 The recognition and prevalence of *Bacteroides nodosus* serotype M in Australia and New Zealand. *Australian Veterinary Journal*. 68: 154-155.
- Clark B L, Stewart D J, and Emery D L 1985 The role of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and *Bacteroides melaninogenicus* in the aetiology of interdigital necrobacillosis in cattle. *Aust. Vet. J.* 62, 47-9.
- Claxton P D and O'Grady K C 1986 Footrot in goats and characterisation of caprine isolates of *Bacteroides nodosus*. In: Stewart D J, Peterson J E, McKern N M & Emery D L Footrot in Ruminants. Proceedings of a workshop, Melbourne 1985. CSIRO Division of Animal Health and Australian Wool Corporation. Sydney, pp. 119-23.
- Claxton P D, Ribeiro L A and Egerton J R 1983 Classification of *Bacteroides nodosus* by agglutination tests. *Australian Veterinary Journal* 60: 331-334.
- Clifton R, Green L E and Purdy J K 2018 Development and validation of a multiple locus variable number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) scheme for *Fusobacterium necrophorum* *Veterinary Microbiology* 213: 108-113.
- Coetzer J, Thomson G, Tustin R and Kriek N 1994 Infectious diseases of livestock: with special reference to southern Africa, Oxford University Press Cape Town.
- Conrads G, Claros MC, Citron DM, Tyrrell KL, Merriam V, and Goldstein EJC 2002

16S-23S rDNA internal transcribed spacer sequences for analysis of the phylogenetic relationships among species of the genus *Fusobacterium*. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 52:493–499.

Conrads G, Marina C, Claros Diane M. Citron, Kerin L Tyrrell, Vreni Merriam and Ellie J C. Goldstein 16S–23S rDNA internal transcribed spacer sequences for analysis of the phylogenetic relationships among species of the genus *Fusobacterium*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* (2002), 52, 493–499.

Corner L A, Collins N D, and Vaughan J A 1996 An experimental ovine foot abscess model using a *Fusobacterium necrophorum* biotype AB. *Vet. Microbiol.* 48, 1-7.

Coyle-Dennis J.E. and Lauerman LH 1978 Biological and chemical characteristics of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* leukotoxin. *American Journal of Veterinary Research*, 39, 1790-1793.

J F, Whittier W D, Currin N 2009 Foot Rot in Beef Cattle. Publication 400-310. Virginia Cooperative extension. Blacksburg, Virginia.

Davenport R, Heawood C, Sessford K, Baker M, Baiker K, Blacklaws B, Kaler, J Green, and L Töttemeyer 2014 Differential expression of Toll-like receptors and inflammatory cytokines in ovine interdigital dermatitis and footrot. *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.*

De Gasparin A E P 1821 Des maladies contagieuses des bêtes à laine. Huzard, Paris, France. Cited by Beveridge, W.I.B. (1981).

De whirst F E, Paster, B J, La Fontaine S, and Rood J I 1990 Transfer of *Kingella indologenes* (Snell and Lapage 1976) to the genus *Suttonella* gen. nov. as *Suttonella indologenes* comb. nov.; transfer of *Bacteroides nodosus* (Beveridge 1941) to the genus *Dichelobacter* gen. nov. as *Dichelobacter nodosus* comb. nov.; and assignment of the genera *Cardiobacterium*, *Dichelobacter*, and *Suttonella* to *Cardiobacteriaceae* fam. nov. in the gamma division of Proteobacteria on the basis of 16S rRNA sequence comparisons. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 40, 426-433.

- De whitter 2009 Control, Treatment, and Elimination of Foot Rot from Sheep, Virginia Cooperative extension 410-028.
- Depiazzi L J and Richards R B 1985 Motility in relation to virulence of *Bacteroides nodosus*. *Veterinary Microbiology* 10: 107-116.
- Depiazzi L J, Henderson J, and Penhale W J 1990 Measurement of protease thermostability, twitching motility and colony size of *Bacteroides nodosus*. *Veterinary microbiology* 22, 353-363.
- Depiazzi LJ, Roberts W.D, Hawkins C D, Palmer M A, Pitman D R, McQuade N C, Jelinek P D, Devereaux D J, and Rippon R J 1998 Severity and persistence of footrot in Merino sheep experimentally infected with a protease thermostable strain of *Dichelobacter nodosus* at five sites. *Australian Veterinary Journal* 76: 32-38.
- Dhungyel O P, Whittington R J and Egerton J R 2002 Serogroup specific single and multiplex PCR with pre-enrichment culture and immuno-magnetic bead capture for identifying strains of *D.nodosus* in sheep with footrot prior to vaccination. *Molec. cell. Probes*, 16 (4), 285–296.
- Dhungyel O, Hunter J, and Whittington R, 2014. Footrot vaccines and vaccination. *Vaccine* 32, 3139–3146.
- Dixit S P, Chander R, Kumar S, and Dhillon J S 2006 Status of newly developed wool strains of sheep in India – a review. *Agric. Rev.*27:292–297.
- Dorsch M, Lovet D N, and Bailey G D 2001 *Fusobacterium equinum*, from the oral cavity of horses. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 51, 1959– 1963.
- Downes J, King A, Hardie J, and Phillips I 1999 Evaluation of the Rapid ID 32A system for identification of anaerobic Gram-negative bacilli, excluding the *Bacteroides fragilis* group. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 5:319–326.
- Egerton J R 1970 Successful vaccination of sheep against footrot *Aus. Vet. Journal:* 46: 114-5.
- Egerton J R 1973 Surface and somatic antigen of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *Journal of Comparative Pathology* 83: 151-159.

- Egerton J R 1973 Surface and somatic antigens of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *J. Comp Pathol.*, 83: 151-159.
- Egerton J R and Parsonson I M 1966 Isolation of *Fusiformis nodosus* from cattle. *Australian Veterinary Journal*, 42(11), pp. 425-429.
- Egerton J R and Roberts D S 1971 Vaccination against ovine foot-rot. *Journal Comparative Pathology* 81: 179-185.
- Egerton J R, and Thorley C M 1981 Effect of alum-precipitated or oil-adjuvant *Bacteroides nodosus* vaccines on the resistance of sheep to experimental foot rot. *Res Vet Sci.* ;30:28-31.
- Egerton J R, Cox P T, Anderson B J, Kristo C, Norman M and Mattick J S 1987 Protection of sheep against footrot with a recombinant DNA-based fimbrial vaccine. *Vet. Microbiol.*, 14: 393-409.
- Egerton J R, Dhungyel O P, Ghimire S C and Rasali D P 1994 Management of footrot. In Proceedings of the Seminar and on Footrot Eradication Programme in sheep and goats in Nepal Vol. 94- 1 Lumle - Agricultural - Centre, pp . 13-17.
- Egerton J R, Parsonson I M 1966 ISOLATION OF *FUSIFORMIS NODOSUS* FROM CATTLE. *Australian Veterinary Journal* Volume 42, 11: 425-429
- Egerton JR, Roberts DS, and Parsonson IM 1969 The aetiology and pathogenesis of ovine footrot A histological study of the bacterial invasion. *J Comp Pathol* 79:207-216.
- Elleman, T C 1988 Pilins of *Bacteroides nodosus*: molecular basis of serotypic variation and relationships to other bacterial pilins. *Microbiol Rev*, 52:233-247.
- Emery D L, J A Vaughan, B L Clark, and D J Stewart 1986 Virulence determinants of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and their prophylactic potential in animals. p. 267-274. In D J Stewart, J E Peterson, N M McKern, and D L Emery (ed.), Foot rot in Ruminants. Proceedings of a workshop, Melbourne: CSIRO Division of Animal Health, Australian Wool Corporation, Glebe, New South Wales, Australia.

- Emery D L, Stewart D J, and Clark, B L, 1984. The comparative susceptibility of five breeds of sheep to footrot. *Australian veterinary journal* 61, 85-88.
- Emery D L, Vaughan J A, Clark B L, Dufty J H, and Stewart D J, 1985. Cultural characteristics and virulence of strains of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* isolated from the feet of cattle and sheep. *Aust. Vet. J.*
- Enlund, K. (2010). Fotröta hos får: *Dichelobacter nodosus* överlevnad i jord (Footrot in sheep: *Dichelobacter nodosus* survival in soil. Undergraduate thesis. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala.
- Ennen S, Hamann H, Distl O, Hickford J, Zhou H, Ganter M 2009 A field trial to control ovine footrot via vaccination and genetic markers. *Small Ruminant Res*, 86, 22-5.
- Escayg Ab P, Hickford J G, Bullock D W 1997 Association between alleles of the ovine major histocompatibility complex and resistance to footrot. *Res. Vet. Sci.* 63, 283-7.
- Every D and Skerman T M 1982 Protection of sheep against experimental footrot by vaccination with pili purified from *B.nodosus*. *N.Z. Vet. J.* 30:156-158.
- Farooq S, S A Wani, Hassan MN, Nazir N, Nyrah QJ 2015 The detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from ovine footrot in Kashmir, India. *Anaerobe* 35: 41-43.20.
- Farooq S, Wani S A, Hassan M N, Aalamgeer S, Kashoo Z A, Magray S N, and Bhat M.A 2018 The detection and prevalence of leukotoxin gene variant strains of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* in footrot lesions of sheep in Kashmir, India. *Anaerobe* 51, 36–41.
- Farooq S, Wani S A, Hussain I and Bhat M A 2010 Prevalence of ovine footrot in Kashmir, India and molecular characterization of *Dichelobacter nodosus* by PCR. *Indian J. anim. Sci.*, 80 (9), 826–830.
- Fievez L.1963. Étude comparée des souches de *Sphaerophorus necrophorus* isolées chez l'homme et chez l'animal. Brussels: *Presses Académiques Européennes*,

1963.

- Frosth S, Slettemeas JS, Jørgensen HJ, Angen O, and Aspán A 2012 Development and comparison of a real-time PCR assay for detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* with culturing and conventional PCR: harmonisation between three laboratories. *Acta Vet. Scand.* 54:6. 10.1186/1751-0147-54-6.
- Frosth, S., König, U., Nyman, A.K., Pringle, M., and Aspán, A 2015. Characterisation of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and detection of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and *Treponema spp.* in sheep with different clinical manifestations of footrot. *Vet. Microbiol.* 179(1-2), 82-90.
- Fussenegger M, T Rudel, R. Barten, R Ryll, and T F Meyer 1997 Transformation competence and type-4 pilus biogenesis in *Neisseria gonorrhoeaea* review. *Gene* 192:125–134.
- Ghimire S C, Egerton J R, and Dhungyel O P 1996 Characterisation of *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolated from footrot in sheep and goats in Nepal. *Small Ruminant Research* 23, 59-67.
- Ghimire S C, Egerton J R, Dhungyel O P and Joshi H D 1998 Identification and Characterisation of serogroup M among Nepalese isolates of *Dichelobacter nodosus*, the transmitting agent of footrot in small ruminants. *Veterinary Microbiology* 62: 217- 233.
- Gilhuus M, Vatn S, Dhungyel O P, Tesfamichael B, L'Abée Lund, T.M., and Jørgensen H J 2013 Characterisation of *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolates from Norway. *Veterinary microbiology* 163, 142-148.
- Glynn T, 1993 Benign footrot an epidemiological investigation into the occurrence, effects on production, response to treatment and influence of environmental factors. *Australian Veterinary Journal* 70, 7–12.
- Gradin J L, Schmitz J A. 1977. Selective medium for isolation of *Bacteroides nodosus*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 6, 298-302.
- Gradin JL, Sonn AE, Petrovska L. Serogrouping of *Bacteroides nodosus* isolates from 62 sources in the United States. *Am J Vet Res* 1993 ; 54 : 1069 -1073.

- Graham N P H, and Egerton J R 1968 Pathogenesis of ovine footrot: the role of some environmental factors. *Aust. Vet. J.* 44, 235–240.
- Graupner S, V Frey, R Hashemi, M G Lorenz, G Brandes, and W Wackernagel 2000 Type IV pilus genes *pilA* and *pilC* of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* are required for natural genetic transformation, and *pilA* can be replaced by corresponding genes from nontransformable species. *J. Bacteriol.* 182:2184–2190.
- Green L E, and George T R 2008 Assessment of current knowledge of footrot in sheep with particular reference to *Dichelobacter nodosus* and implications for elimination or control strategies for sheep in Great Britain. *Vet J* 175, 173-180.
- Guasp C, Moore E R B, Lalucat J. & Bennasar A 2000 Utility of internally transcribed 16S–23S rDNA spacer regions for the definition of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* genomovars and other *Pseudomonas* species. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 50, 1629–1639.
- Gurtler, V 1999 The role of recombination and mutation in 16S-23SrDNA spacer rearrangements. *Gene* 238, 241–252.
- Hagelskjær K L, Prag J 2008 Localised *Fusobacterium necrophorum* infections: A prospective laboratory-based Danish study. *Eur. J. Clin. Microbiol. Infect. Dis.* 27, 733–739.
- Han X, Kennan R M, Parker D, Davies J K, and Rood J I, 2007 Type IV fimbrial biogenesis is required for protease secretion and natural transformation in *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *J Bacteriol* 189, 5022-5033.
- Hindmarsh, F. and Fraser, J 1985 Serogrouping of *Bacteroides nodosus* isolated from ovine footrot in Britain. *Veterinary Record* 116: 187-188.
- Hobbs M, Dalrymple B P, Cox P T, Livingstone S P, Delaney S F and Mattick J S 1991 Organization of the fimbrial gene region of *Bacteroides nodosus*: class I and class II strains. *Mol Microbiol*, 5:543-560.
- Hobbs M, and J S Mattick 1993 Common components in the assembly of type fimbriae, DNA transfer systems, filamentous phage and protein secretion

apparatus: a general system for the formation of surface-associated protein complexes. *Mol. Microbiol.* 10:233–243.

Hofstad T. The genus *Fusobacterium*. In: Dworkin M, Falkow S, Rosenberg E, Schleifer K H, Stackebrandt E 2006 The Prokaryotes. Volume 7: *Proteobacteria: Delta, Epsilon Subclass*. Springer. pp. 1016–1027.

Hudson, Don, "Foot Rot" 1982 Historical Materials from University of Nebraska-Lincoln Extension. 6.

Hurtado M A, Piriz S, Valle J, Jimenez R and Vadillo S 1998 Aetiology of ovine footrot in Spain. *Veterinary Record* 142: 60-63.

I, SA Wani, SD Qureshi, S Farooq, Serological diversity and virulence determination of *Dichelobacter nodosus* from footrot in India. *Mol Cell Probes*. 2009; 23: 112-114.

Inoue T, Kanoe M, Goto N, Matsumura K and Nakano K 1985 Chemical and biological properties of lipopolysaccharides from *Fusobacterium necrophorum* biovar A and biovar B strains. *Japanese Journal of Veterinary Science*, 47, 639-645.

Iteman I, Rippka R, Tandeau De Marsac N and Herdman M 2000 Comparison of conserved structural and regulatory domains within divergent 16S rRNA–23S rRNA spacer sequences of *cyanobacteria*. *Microbiology* 146, 1275–1286.

James T S and Whitman W B 2010 The animal biotype A group clearly corresponds to *F. necrophorum* subsp *hemolysis* on rabbit blood agar *Veterinary Microbiology* 54,110-112.

Jang S S and Hirsh D W 1994 Characterization, distribution, and microbiological associations of *Fusobacterium spp.* in clinical specimens of animal origin. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 322, 384 387

Jansen GJ, Mooibroek M, Idema J, Harmsen HJ, Welling GW, and Degener JE 2000 Rapid identification of bacteria in blood cultures by using fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide probes. *J Clin Microbiol* 38:814–817.

Jessen P, Kristiansen O, and Madaan F O 1993 *Baquiloprim* in calves and young

cattle, Oral treatment of enzootic pneumonia and infectious Dansk Veterinary 76: 796 to 798.

R, Piriz S, Martin Palomino, Mateose M and Vadillo S 2003 Aetiology of ovine footrot in the Portuguese region of Alto Alentejo. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine B* 59:118-120.

John G H, Carlson J O, Kimberling C V and Ellis R P 1990 Polymerase Chain Reaction Amplification of Constant and Variable Regions of the *Bacteroides nodosus* Fimbrial Gene. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 140, Council for Scientific and biological 28, 2456–61.

John G, Smith R, Abraham KJ, and Ellis R P 1999 Identification and grouping of *Dichelobacter nodosus*, using PCR and sequence analysis. *Mol. and Cel. Prob.* 13: 61–65.

Kanoe M, Ishii T, Mizutani K and Blobel H 1986 Partial characterization of leukotoxin from *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *Zentralblatt für Bakteriologie und Hygiene*, 261, 170-176.

Kanoe M, Iriki M and Ishii M 1984 Effect of *fusobacterium necrophorum* haemolysin on peripheral leukocytes in vitro. *Fems Microbiology Letters* 28:187-191.

Katz M E, Howarth P M, Yong W K, Riffkin G G, Depiazzi L J and Rood J I 1991 Identification of three gene regions associated with virulence in *Dichelobacter nodosus*, the causative agent of ovine footrot. *Journal of General Microbiology*, 137(9), pp. 2117-24

Kaufmann P, Pfefferkorn A, Teuber M, and Meile L 1997 Identification and quantification of *Bifidobacterium* species isolated from food with genus-specific 16S rRNA targeted probes by colony hybridization and PCR. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 63:1268–1273.

Kennan R M, Wong W, Dhungyel O P, HAN X, Wong D, and Parker D 2010 the subtilisin-like protease *AprV2* is required for virulence and uses a novel disulphide-tethered exosite to bind substrates. *PLoS Pathogens* 6, 1001210.

Kennan R M, Dhungyel O P, Whittington R J, Egerton J R and Rood J I 2003

Transformation-mediated serogroup conversion of *Dichelobacter nodosus* *Veterinary Microbiology*, 92(1-2), pp. 169-78.

Kennan R M, Dhungyel O P, Whittington R J, Egerton J R and Rood J I 2001 The type IV fimbrial subunit gene *fimA* of *Dichelobacter nodosus* is essential for virulence, protease secretion, and natural competence. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 183(15), pp. 4451-8.

Kennan R M, Han X, Porter C J, and Rood J I, 2011 The pathogenesis of ovine footrot. *Vet Microbiol* 153, 59-66.

Kingsley D L, Hindmarsh F, Liardet D M and Chetwin D H 1986 Footrot in ruminants. In: Stewart D J, Peterson J E, Mckern N M and Emery D L, Melbourne, CSIRO. P. 143.

Knappe-Poindecker M, Gilhuus M, Jensen T K, Vatn S Jørgensen, H J and Fjeldaas, T. 2014a Cross-infection of virulent *Dichelobacter nodosus* between sheep and co-grazing cattle. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 170(3-4), pp. 375-82.

Knappe-Poindecker M, Jørgensen H J, Jensen T K, Tesfamichael B, Ulvund M J, Hektoen L and Fjeldaas T. 2015 Experimental infection of cattle with ovine *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolates. *Acta Veterinaria Scandinavica*, 57(1), pp. 15.

Knappe-Poindecker, M, Jørgensen H J, Jensen T K, Tesfamichael B, Ulvund M J, Vatn S and Fjeldaas T. 2014b Experimental infection of sheep with ovine and bovine *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolates. *Small Ruminant Research*, 121, pp. 411-7.

Kumar A, Anderson D, Amachawadi RG, Nagaraja T G, Narayanan S K 2013 Characterization of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* isolated from llama and alpaca. *J. Vet. Diagnostic Investig.* 25, 502–507.

Kumar S, Stecher G, and Tamura K 2016 MEGA7: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis version 7.0 *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 33:1870-1874

La Fontaine S, and Rood J 1996 Organization of ribosomal RNA genes from the footrot pathogen *Dichelobacter nodosus*, *Microbiology*.142:889-99.

La Fontaine S, Egerton J R and Rood J I 1993 Detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus*

- using species-specific oligonucleotides as PCR primers. *Vet. Microbiol.* 35, 101-117.
- Langendijk P S, Schut F, Jansen G J, Raangs G C, Kamphuis G R, Wilkinson M H F, Welling G W 1995 Quantitative fluorescence in situ hybridization of *Bifidobacterium* spp. with genus-specific 16S rRNA-targeted probes and its application in fecal samples. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 61:3069–3075.
- Langworth B F 1977 *Fusobacterium necrophorum* its characteristics and role as an animal pathogen. *Bacteriol. Rev.* 41, 373–390.
- Liardet DM, Chetwin DH, McNerney DM, and Hindmarsh FH 1989 Reduction of the prevalence of footrot on New Zealand farms by vaccination. *N Z Vet J* 37:129–30.
- Lin C, Raskin L, Stahl D A 1997 Microbial community structure in gastrointestinal tracts of domestic animals: comparative analyses using rRNA-targeted oligonucleotide probes. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 22:281–294.
- Lindstedt BA. Multiple-locus variable number tandem repeats analysis for genetic fingerprinting of pathogenic bacteria. *Electrophoresis* 2005; 26: 2567–2582.
- Links I J, and Morris S 1996 Assessment of gelatin gel and elastase tests for detection of protease activity of *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolates from ovine footrot *Veterinary Microbiology* 51 (1996) 305-318.
- Litchfield A M, Raadsma H W, Hulme D J, Brown S C, Nicholas F W, Egerton J R 1993 Disease resistance in merino sheep. II. RFLPs in Class 2 MHC and their association with footrot. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 110, 321-34.
- Liu D, Roycroft C, Samuel J, and Webber J 1994 A retrospective study of clinical and laboratory characteristics of ovine footrot. *Vet Microbiol.* 42(4):373–381.
- Liu D, Yong W K 1995 Molecular basis for the virulence of *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Trends in Microbiology* 3, 474-475.
- Ludlam H A, Milner N J, Brazier J S, Davies I H, Perry K, Marriott R K, Donachie L, and Curran M D 2009 *lktA*-encoded leukotoxin is not a universal virulence factor in invasive *Fusobacterium necrophorum* infections in animals and man.

J. Med. Microbiol. 58, 529-30.

Lunestad B T, T T T Truong and B A Linsted 2013 A multiple-locus variable-number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) of *Listeria monocytogenes* isolated from Norwegian salmon-processing factories and from listeriosis patients *Epidemiol Infect.* 141, 2101–2110.

Maboni G, Davenport R, Sessford K, Blanchard A, Entrican G, Wattegedera S, Rutland C and Totemeyer S 2016 3D culture model for ovine footrot: generating an alternative to in vivo research The 4th Prato 64 Conference on the Pathogenesis of Bacterial Infections of Animals Prato, Italy.

Marcos Pérez-Losadaa, Miguel Arenasd, Eduardo Castro-Nallar 2017 Microbial sequence typing in the genomic era. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*,63, 346-359.

Marshall D J, Walker R J, Cullis B R, Luff M F 1991 The effect of footrot on body weight and wool growth of sheep. *Australian Veterinary Journal* 68, 45–49.

Mattick J S, Anderson B J, Cox P T, Bills M M, Dalrymple B and Egerton J R 1991 Gene sequences and comparison of the fimbrial subunits representative of *Bacteroides nodosus* serogroups A to I: class I and class II strains. *Mol. Micro.* 5:561-573.

Mittal J P, and Ghosh P K 1979 Comparative performance of indigenous and exotic sheep in the Indian arid zone. *J. Agric. Sci.*;92:273–276.

Mohler J, and Washburn H 1905 Foot-rot of sheep: its nature, cause and treatment. Government Printing Office, Washington, USA.

Moore L J, Wassink, G J, Green, L E, and Thomas G R 2005 The detection and characterisation of *Dichelobacter nodosus* from cases of ovine footrot in England and Wales. *Veterinary microbiology* 108, 57-67.

Moore LV, Bourne D M, and Moore W E 1994 Comparative distribution and taxonomic value of cellular fatty acids in thirty-three genera of anaerobic gram-negative bacilli. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 44:338–347.

Morgenstein A A, Citron D M, and Finegold S M 1981 New medium selective for

Fusobacterium species and differential for *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 13, 666–669.

Motoyama Y and Ogata T 2000 16S–23S rDNA spacer of *Pectinatus*, *Selenomonas* and *Zymophilus* reveal new phylogenetic relationships between these genera. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 50,883–886.

Muzafar M, Calvo-Bado L A, Green L E, Smith E M, Russell C L, Grogono- Thomas R and Wellington E M 2015 The role of the environment in transmission of *Dichelobacter nodosus* between ewes and their lambs. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 179(1-2), pp. 53-9.

Muzafar M, Green L E, Calvo-Bado L A, Tichauer E, King H, James P and Wellington E M 2016 Survival of the ovine footrot pathogen *Dichelobacter nodosus* in different soils. *Anaerobe*, 38, pp. 81-7.

Myers G S, Parker D, Al-Hasani K, Kennan R M, Seemann T, Ren Q, Badger J H, Selengut J D, Deboy R T, Tettelin H, Boyce J D, McCarl V P, Han X, Nelson W C, Madupu R, Mohamoud Y, Holley T, Fedorova N, Khouri H, Bottomley S P, Whittington R J, Adler B, Songer J G, Rood J I and Paulsen I T 2007 Genome sequence and identification of candidate vaccine antigens from the animal pathogen *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Nature Biotechnology*, 25(5), pp. 569-75.

Nagaraja T G, Narayanan S K, Stewart G C, Chengappa M M 2005 *Fusobacterium necrophorum* infections in animals: Pathogenesis and pathogenic mechanisms. *Anaerobe* 11, 239–246.

Nakajima Y, Nakamura K, and Takeuchi S 1985 Effects of the components of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* in experimental liver abscess formation in mice. *Japanese Journal of Veterinary Science*, 47,589-595.

Nakajima Y, Ueda H and Takeuchi S 1988 Synergistic effects of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* lipopolysaccharide, cytoplasmic, and culture supernatant fractions on induction of acute hepatic necrosis in rabbits. *American Journal of Veterinary Research*, 49, 125-129.

Narayanan S K, Chengappa M M, Stewart G C, Nagaraja T G 2003 Immunogenicity

- and protective effects of truncated recombinant leukotoxin proteins of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* in mice. *Veterinary Microbiology* 93, 335–347.
- Narayanan S K, Nagaraja T G, Chengappa M M, Stewart GC 2001 Electrophoretic mobility anomalies associated with PCR amplification of the intergenic spacer region between 16S and 23S ribosomal RNA genes of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *J Microbiol Methods*;46:165–9.
- Narayanan, S K, Stewart G C, Chengappa M M, Willard L Shuman, W Wilkerson, and Nagaraja T G 2002 *Fusobacterium necrophorum* Leukotoxin Induces Activation and Apoptosis of Bovine Leukocytes. *Infect. Immun.* 70, 4609–4620.
- Nayakwadi S, Gupta V K, Sharma N, Mishra A K, Singh V K, Pawaiya R S, Gururaj K, Sharma D K, Kumar A, Paul S, Navven Kumar, and Singh S V 2014 Rapid detection of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* as main causative agent of footrot in small ruminants by PCR assay. *Adv. Anim. Vet. Sci.* 2 (5): 302-304.
- Naylor RD, Martin PK, Jones JR, and Burnell MC 1998 Isolation of spirochaetes from an incident of severe virulent ovine footrot *Vet Rec.* Dec 19-26;143(25):690-1.
- Oelke A M, Nagaraja T G, Wilkerson M J, and Stewart G C 2005 The leukotoxin operon of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* is not present in other species of *Fusobacterium*. *Anaerobe* 11, 123–129.
- Okahashi N, Koga T, Nisbihara T, Fujiwara T. and Hamada S 1988 Immunobiological properties of lipopolysaccharides isolated from *Fusobacterium nucleatum* and *F.necrophorum*. *Journal of General Microbiology*,134, 1707-1715.
- Olson M E, Gard S and Morck D W 1998 Serological classification and virulence determination of *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolated from Alberta and British Columbia sheep. *Canadian Journal of Veterinary Research* 62: 33-37.
- Outteridge P M, Stewart D J, Skerman T M, Dufty J H, Egerton J R, Ferrier G, and Marshall D J 1989 A positive association between resistance to ovine footrot and particular lymphocyte antigen types. *Aust. Vet. J.* 66, 175-9.

- Parker D, Kennan R.M, Myers G S, Paulsen I T, Songer J G, and Rood J I 2006 Regulation of type IV fimbrial biogenesis in *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *J. Bacteriol.* 188, 4801-11.
- Parsonson, I M, Egerton J R, and Roberts D S 1967 Ovine interdigital dermatitis. *J. Comp. Pathol.*9975(67)90040-0.
- Perez Luz, S., Rodriguez-Valera, F., Lan, R. & Reeves, P. R 1998 Variation of the ribosomal operon 16S-23S gene spacer region in representatives of *Salmonella enterica subspecies*. *J Bacteriol* 180,2144–2151.
- Piriz S, Cuenca R, Valle J and Vadillo S 1990 Isolation and Identification of anaerobic bacteria from ovine footrot in Spain. *Research in Veterinary Science* 49: 245-247.
- Piriz S, Hurtado M A, Valle J Maetos E M, Martin-Palomino O and Vadillo S 1996 Bacteriological study of footrot in Pigs: a preliminary note:*Veterinary Record* 139: 17-19.
- Popoff MR 1991 Causal agent of foot rot: description, pathogenicity, vaccination. *Revue-deMedecine-Veterinaire*.142:453–462.
- Poppert S, Essig A, Stoehr B, Steingruber A, Wirths B, Juretschko S, Reischl U, Wellinghausen N 2005 Rapid diagnosis of bacterial meningitis by real-time PCR and fluorescence in situ hybridization. *J Clin Microbiol* 43:3390–3397.
- Preacher, K. J. 2001, April Calculation for the chi-square test: An interactive calculation tool for chi-square tests of goodness of fit and independence [Computer software]. Available from <http://quantpsy.org>.
- Rachel Clifton, Laura E Green, Kevin J Purdy 2018 Development and validation of a multiple locus variable number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA) scheme for *Fusobacterium necrophorum* . *Veterinary Microbiology* 213 (2018) 108–113.
- Rather M A, Wani S A, Hussain I, Bhat M A, Kabli Z A and Magray S.N 2011 Determination of prevalence and economic impact of ovine footrot in central Kashmir India with isolation and molecular characterization of *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Anaerobe*, 17 (2), 73–77.
- Rebecca D, Christopher H, Kate S, Melissa B, and Kerstin B 2014 Differential

expression of Toll-like receptors and inflammatory cytokines in ovine interdigital dermatitis and footrot. *Vet Immunol Immunopathol* 161: 90-98.

Riffkin M C, Wang L F, Kortt A A and Stewart D J 1995 A single aminoacid change between the antigenically different extracellular serine proteases V2 and B2 from *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Gene*, 167(1-2), pp. 279-83.

Roberts D S and Egerton J R 1969 The aetiology and pathogenesis of ovine foot-rot. II. The pathogenic association of *Fusiformis nodosus* and *F. necrophorus*. *J Comp Pathol*, 79:217-227.

Roberts D S 1967 The pathogenic synergy of *Fusiformis necrophorus* and *Corynebacterium pyogenes*. Influence of the leukocidal exotoxin of *F. necrophorus*. *British Journal of Experimental Pathology*, 48, 665-673.

Roberts D S, Graham N P H, Egerton J R, Parsonson I M 1968 Infective bulbar necrosis (heel-abscess) of sheep, a mixed infection with *Fusiformis necrophorus* and *Corynebacterium pyogenes*. *J. Comp. Pathol.* 21-68.

Roy R K and Misger F 2010 Footrot in sheep in Kashmir valley 28 (1): 722-723.

Russell C L, Smith E M, Calvo Bado L A, Green L E, Wellington E M, Medley G F, Moore L J, and Thomas G R 2014 Multiple locus VNTR analysis highlights that geographical clustering and distribution of *Dichelobacter nodosus*, the causal agent of footrot in sheep, correlates with inter-Country 159 movements. *Infection, genetics and evolution: journal of molecular epidemiology and evolutionary genetics in infectious diseases* 22, 273-279.

Scanlan C M, Berg J N, and Campbell F F 1986 Biochemical characterization of the leukotoxins of three bovine strains of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *Am. J. Vet. Res.* 47, 1422-1425.

Scanlan C M, Berg J N, and Fales W H, 1982 Comparative in vitro leukotoxin production of three bovine strains of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *Am. J. Vet. Res.* 43, 1329-1333.

Schmitz J A and Gradin J L 1980 Serotypic and Biochemical Characterization of *Bacteroides nodosus* Isolates from Oregon.

Schmitz J A and Gradin J L 1980 Serotypic and Biochemical Characterization of *Bacteroides nodosus* Isolates from Oregon.

- Seaman John, Evers M 2006 Footrot in sheep and goats. Prime facts NSW Department of Primary Industries.
- Shaheen F 2013 Molecular characterization of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from ovine footrot and identification of its major immunoreactive outer membrane proteins P.hd Thesis Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Kashmir.
- Sharon La Fontaine, John R Egerton and Julian I Rood 1993 Detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* using species-specific oligonucleotides as PCR primers. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 35 (1993) 101-117.
- Shinjo T 1983 *Fusobacterium necrophorum* isolated from a hepatic and from mastitic udder secretions in a heifer. *Ann Microbiol* 134B: 401-409.
- Shinjo T, Fujisawa T and Mitsuoka T 1991 Proposal of two subspecies of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* (Flugge) Moore and Holdeman: *Fusobacterium necrophorum* subsp. *necrophorum* subsp. nov., nom. rev.(ex Flugge 1886), and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* subsp. *Funduliforme* subsp. nov., nom. rev. (ex Halle 1898). *International Journal of Systematic Bacteriology*, 41, 395-397.
- Shinjo T, Miyazato S, Kane I C and Mitsuoka T 1981 Physiological and biochemical characteristics of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* biovar A and biovar B strains and their deoxyribonucleic acid homology. *Japanese Journal of Veterinary Science*, 43, 233-241.
- Sigge, Anja, Essig, Andreas Wirths, Beate Fickweiler, Kristina, Kaestner, Nicole Wellinghausen, Nele , Poppert, Sven 2007 Rapid identification of *Fusobacterium nucleatum* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* by fluorescence in situ hybridization. *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease* 58: 255–259.
- Skerman T M, Moorhouse S R 1987 Broomfield *corriedales*: a strain of sheep selectively bred for resistance to footrot. *N. Z. Vet. J.* 35, 101-6.
- Skerman, T M 1975 Determination of some in vitro growth requirements of *Bacteroides nodosus*. *Journal of General Microbiology*, 87(1), pp. 107-19.

- Skerman, T M 1983 Isolation of *Bacteroides nodosus* from hoof lesions in a farmed red deer (*Cervus elaphus*). *The New Zealand Veterinary Journal*, 31(6), pp. 102-3.
- Skerman, T M, Erasmuson S K and Every D 1981 Differentiation of *Bacteroides nodosus* biotypes and colony variants in relation to their virulence and immunoprotective properties in sheep. *Infection and Immunity*, 32(2), pp. 788-95.
- Smith G R, and Thornton E A 1993 The prevalence of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* biovar A in animal faeces. *Epidemiol. Infect.* 110, 327–331.
- Soller R, Hirsch P, Blohm D and Labrenz M 2000 Differentiation of newly described Antarctic bacterial isolates related to *Roseobacter species* based on 16S–23S rDNA internal transcribed spacer sequences. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 50, 909–915.
- Sreenivasulu D, Vijayalakshmi S, Raniprameela D, Karthik A, and Wani S A, Hussain, I 2013 Prevalence of ovine footrot in the tropical climate of southern India and isolation and characterisation of *Dichelobacter nodosus*. *Rev. Sci. Tech. Int. Des Epizoot.* 32, 869–877.
- Stäuble A, Steiner A, Frey J and Kuhnert P 2014 Simultaneous detection and discrimination of virulent and benign *Dichelobacter nodosus* in sheep of flocks affected by foot rot and in clinically healthy flocks by competitive real-time PCR. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 52(4), pp. 1228-31.
- Stewart D J 1978 The role of various antigenic fractions of *Bacteroides nodosus* in eliciting protection against foot-rot in vaccinated sheep. *Res. Vet Sci.*, 24: 14-19.
- Stewart D J 1973 An electron microscopic study of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *Res. Vet. Sci.* 14 132-114.
- Stewart D J 1979 The role of elastase in the differentiation of *Bacteroides nodosus* infections in sheep and cattle. *Research in Veterinary Science*, 27(1), pp. 99-

105.

- Stewart D J 1989 Footrot in sheep In Egerton J R, Yong W K, Yong W K, Riffikin G G Footrot and Foot Abscesses of ruminants. C R C press, Boca Raton, FL, 5-45.
- Stewart D J, Peterson J E, Vaughan J A, Clark B L, Emery D L, Caldwell J B and Kortt A A 1986 The pathogenicity and cultural characteristics of virulent, intermediate and benign strains of *Bacteroides nodosus* causing ovine foot-rot. *Australian Veterinary Journal*, 63(10), pp. 317-26.
- Strom M S and S Lory 1993 Structure-function and biogenesis of the type IV pili. *Annu. Rev. Microbiol.* 47:565–596.
- Summanen P, and Jousimies-Somer H 1988 Comparative evaluation of RapID ANA and API 20 A for identification of anaerobic bacteria. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis* 7:771–775.
- Sun D B, Wu R, Li G L, Zheng J S, Liu X P, Lin Y C, and Guo D H 2009 Identification of three immunodominant regions on leukotoxin protein of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *Veterinary Research Communications* 33, 749–755.
- Tadepalli B 2007 Leukotoxin gene and activity in animal and human strains of *fusobacterium species* Thesis Kansas State University.
- Tamura K, Dudley J, Nei M and Kumar S 2007 MEGA4: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) software version 4.0. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 24:1596-1599.
- Tan Z L, Nagaraja T G and Chengappa M M 1994 Biochemical and biological characterization of ruminal *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 120, 81-86.
- Tan Z L, Nagaraja T G, and Chengappa M M 1996 *Fusobacterium necrophorum* infections: virulence factors, pathogenic mechanism and control measures. *Vet. Res. Commun.* 20, 113–140.
- Tan Z L, Nagaraja T G, Chengappa M M and Smith J S 1994 Biological and

- biochemical characterization of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *American Journal of Veterinary Research*, 55, 515-521.
- Tan Z L, Nagaraja T G, Chengappa M M, and Smith J S 1994 Biological and biochemical characterization of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* leukotoxin. *Am J Vet Res*.
- Tan Z L, Nagaraja T.G and Chengappa M M 1992 Factors affecting the leukotoxin activity of *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 32, 15-28.
- Tanner A, Maiden M F, Paster B J, and Dewhirst F E 1994 The impact of 16S ribosomal RNA-based phylogeny on the taxonomy of oral bacteria. *Periodontol* 2000 5:26–51.
- Tanner AC, Strzempko M N, Belsky C A, McKinley G A 1985 An-Ident reactions of fastidious oral gram-negative species. *J Clin Microbiol* 22:333–335.
- Thomas J H 1958 A simple medium for the isolation and cultivation of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *Australian veterinary journal* 34, 411.
- Thomas J H 1964 The pathogenesis of footrot in sheep with reference to proteases of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *Aust. J. Agric. Res.* 15, 1001–1016.
- Thomas J H, 1962 The differential diagnosis of footrot in sheep. *Australian veterinary journal* 38, 366-367.
- Thomas N, Joseph S, Alex R, Raghavan K C, Radhika G, Anto L, Mohan S G 2011 Genetic variation in resistance to caprine foot rot by *Dichelobacter nodosus* in goats of Kerala, India. *Biotechnol. Anim. Hus.* 27, 235-240.
- Thorley C M 1976 A simplified method for the isolation of *Bacteroides nodosus* from ovine foot-rot and studies on its colony morphology and serology. *Journal Applied Bacteriology* 40: 301-309.
- Thorley C M and Day S E J 1986 A simple medium for the isolation and cultivation of *Fusiformis nodosus*. *Australian Veterinary Journal* 34:411.
- Toussaint E R and Cornelisse J L 1971 The specific contagious inflammation of the

interdigital skin of cattle. *Veterinary Medicine review* : 2-3.

- Trebesius K, Panthel K, Strobel S, Vogt K, Faller G, Kirchner T, Kist M, Heesemann J, Haas R 2000 Rapid and specific detection of *Helicobacter pylori* macrolide resistance in gastric tissue by fluorescent in situ hybridisation. *Gut* 46:608–614.
- Van Belkum A 2007 Tracing isolates of bacterial species by multilocus variable number of tandem repeat analysis (MLVA). *Immunology and Medical Microbiology* 49: 22–27.
- Vinod Kumar N, Karthik A, Sreenivasulu D 2016 Detection of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from footrot of sheep and goats in Andhra Pradesh. *Indian Vet. J.* 93, 39–41.
- Vinod Kumar N, Karthik A, Sreenivasulu D, Vijayalakshmi S, and Vijaya Bhaskhar M 2013 Incidence of footrot in summer at Thottambedu and B.N. Kandriga mandals of Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. *Int. J. adv. Sci. Tech. Res.* 07: 248-56.
- Vinod Kumar N, Karthik A, Vijaya lakshmi S and Sreenivasulu D 2015 Phylogenetic analysis of *Dichelobacter nodosus* serogroup-specific *fimA* gene from ovine footrot in Andhra Pradesh. *Veterinary World.* 8(5): 567-57.
- W. Dee Whittier 2005 Control, Treatment, and Elimination of Foot Rot from Sheep virginia cooperative extension Publication 410-028.
- Walker P D, Short J, Thomson R O, Roberts D S 1973 The fine structure of *Fusiformis nodosus* with special reference to the location of antigens associated with immunogenicity. *J. Gen. Microbiol.* 77, 351– 361.
- Wani S A Samanta I 2006 Current understanding of the aetiology and laboratory diagnosis of footrot. *Vet. J.* 171, 421–428.
- Wani S A, Samanta I, and Kawoosa S 2007 Isolation and characterization of *Dichelobacter nodosus* from ovine and caprine footrot in Kashmir, India. *Res Vet Sci* 83, 141-144.
- Wani S A, Samanta I, Buchh A S and Bhat MA 2004 Molecular detection and

- characterization of *Dichelobacter nodosus* in ovine footrot in India. *Molec. Cell. Probes*, 18 (5), 289–291.
- Wassink G J, Grogono Thomas R, Moore L J, Green, L E 2003 Risk factors associated with the prevalence of footrot in sheep from 1999 to 2000. *Vet. Rec.* 152, 351-358.
- Whittier W D, Umberger S H, 2009 Control, Treatment, and Elimination of Foot Rot from Sheep. Virginia-maryl. Reg. Coll. Vet. Med.
- Whittington R J, and Nicholas, P J 1995 Grading the lesions of ovine footrot. *Research in Veterinary Science* 58, 26–34.
- Whittington, R., Dhungyel, O., Egerton, J. 2004 Eradication of virulent footrot by specific vaccination. Australian Sheep Veterinary Society. Australian Sheep Veterinary Society.
- Wilkinson F C, Egerton J R and Dickson J 1970 Transmission of *Fusiformis nodosus* infection from cattle to sheep. *Australian Veterinary Journal*, 46(8), pp. 382-4.
- Winter A 2004 Lameness in sheep. Crowood Press.
- Witcomb L A 2014 A longitudinal study of the role of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* load in initiation and severity of footrot in sheep, *Prev. Vet. Med.* 115 48-55.
- Witcomb L A, Green L E, Calvo bado, L A russel, C L smith, E M Grogono Thomas R, and Wellington E M H 2015 First study of pathogen load and localisation of ovine footrot using fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH). *Veterinary Microbiology* 176, 321-327.
- Witcomb L A, Green L E, Kaler J, Ul Hassan A, Calvo Bado L A, Medley G F, Grogono Thomas, R Wellington, E M H 2014 A longitudinal study of the role of *Dichelobacter nodosus* and *Fusobacterium necrophorum* load in initiation and severity of footrot in sheep. *Prev. Vet. Med.* 115, 48–55.
- Witte C, De Flahou B, Ducatelle R, Smet A, Eruyne E, De Cnockaert M, Taminiou B, Daube G, Vandamme P, Haesebrouck F 2016 Detection, isolation and characterization of *Fusobacterium gastrosuis* sp. nov. colonizing the stomach of pigs. *Systematic and Applied Microbiology.*, 40,1: 42-50

- Woese C R, Stackebrandt E, Macke T J and Fox G E 1985 A phylogenetic definition of the major eubacterial taxa. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.*, 6:143-151.
- Woese C.R 1987 Bacterial evolution. *Microbiol. Rev.*, 51: 221-271.
- Youatt W 1837 Sheep: Their Breeds, Management and Diseases. Baldwin and Cradock, London, UK, pp. 523. Cited by Beveridge W I B 1981.
- Zakaria Z, Son Radu, Sheikh Omar A R, Mutalib A R, Joseph P G and Rusul G 1998 Molecular analysis of *Dichelobacter nodosus* isolated from footrot in sheep in Malaysia. *Veterinary Microbiology* 62: 243-250.
- Zhang F, Nagaraja T G, George D, and Stewart G C 2006 The two major subspecies of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* have distinct leukotoxin operon promoter regions. *Vet. Microbiol.* 112, 73-78.
- Zhou H and Hickford J G H 2000 Extensive diversity in New Zealand *Dichelobacter nodosus* strains from infected sheep and goats. *Veterinary Microbiology* 71: 13-123.
- Zhou H and Hickford, J G 2001 *Dichelobacter nodosus* serotype M fimbrial subunit gene: implications for serological classification. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 79(4), pp. 367-74.
- Zhou H T, Bennett G, and Hickford J G H 2009 Variation in *Fusobacterium necrophorum* strains present on the hooves of footrot infected sheep, goats and cattle. *Vet. Microbiol.* 135, 363–367.
- Zhou H, Hickford J G H 2008 Clonal polymerase chain reaction-single-strand conformational polymorphism analysis: an effective approach for identifying cloned sequences. *Anal. Biochem.* 378, 111–112.

APPENDIX

Tris Acetate EDTA (TAE) Buffer Stock solution (50X)	-	242 g 57.1 ml
Tris Base Glacial acetic acid 0.5 M EDTA,	-	100 ml
pH - 8 Distilled Water	-	500 ml
Ethidium bromide	-	1.0 g
Distilled water	-	100 ml
Glycerol	-	200 pl
10X TAE Buffer	-	60 pl
1% Bromophenol blue	-	200 pl
10% SDS	-	60 pl
0.5 M EDTA	-	50 pl
Distilled water	-	30 pl